

Humanities and cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud

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ABSTRACT:

The Humanities and Cultural Heritage Open Science Cloud (H2IOSC) project aims to create a federated network of Italian nodes to support four European Research Infrastructures in the Humanities and Cultural Heritage sectors: DARIAH, CLARIN, OPERAS, and E-RIHS. By integrating digital resources, physical instruments, archives, and data services, H2IOSC seeks to advance data-driven research and digital transformation across cultural and creative fields, aligning with FAIR principles for data accessibility.

Within the project, the Institute of Heritage Science (CNR-ISPC) is instrumental, particularly its Milan branch, which leads Task 4.10 focused on “Resources Interoperability: DIGILAB Resources (E-RIHS)” as part of Work Package 4 (WP4). This task emphasizes the mapping of formats, standards, and ontologies essential for Heritage Science, aiming for cross-domain integration and semantic interoperability through DIGILAB—a collaborative platform for data sharing and virtual research in Heritage Science. Key outputs include a semantic mapping of resources and the development of a specialized Heritage Science ontology compatible with international standards like CIDOC CRM. An annex, developed by ISPC’s Lecce branch, further supports interoperability for pilot projects in WP7, with specific applications in illuminated manuscript and diagnostic ontology extensions.

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

CH	Cultural Heritage
CIDOC CRM	CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
DH	Digital Heritage
E-RIHS	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science
H2IOSC	Humanities and Cultural Heritage Open Science Cloud
GUPRI	Globally Unique, Persistent, Resolvable Identifier
HS	Heritage Science
ICCROM	International Centre for the Study of the Preservation and Restoration of Cultural Property
IH	Intangible Heritage
KE	Knowledge Engineering
KR	Knowledge Representation
MC	Material Culture
NH	Natural Heritage
OE	Ontology Engineering
OWL	Web Ontology Language
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RDFS	Resource Description Framework Schema
Task 4.10	Resources interoperability: DIGILAB resources (E-RIHS)
TH	Tangible Heritage
WP4	Working Package 4: Research Infrastructures Nodes and Resources Interoperability
WP3	Working Package 3: Digital Resources Standardization, Consolidation & Alignment
WP7	Working Package 7: Community pilots: Innovative cross-domain services and environments

GLOSSARY

The following glossary provides explanation of key terminology used in the document. It will be available as a full SKOS thesaurus with the ontology documentation, including all the terms relevant for the domain formalization.

Cultural Heritage	Any form of Heritage that is created by humans.
Description Logics	Description Logics (DL) are a family of formal knowledge representation languages that are used to represent the knowledge of an application domain in a structured and well-defined way. They are particularly designed for reasoning about the concepts and relationships within that domain.
Digital Curation	The process of management, preservation, and enhancement of digital data and assets throughout their lifecycle, ensuring their accessibility and usability in the long term. It entails the careful selection, organization, upkeep, and archiving of digital content to safeguard its integrity and significance.
FAIR Data	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable Data. A set of guiding principles aimed at making data easier to find for both humans and machines, formatted in a way that allows it to integrate seamlessly with other datasets, allowing others to understand how it was generated, what it represents, and how it can be used.
Heritage	See paragraph 3 for further details.
Heritage Science	Interdisciplinary research field that combines social sciences and natural sciences applied to Cultural and Natural Heritage.
Intangible Heritage	Any form of Heritage not represented by a tangible entity.
Interoperability	The ability of diverse systems and applications to seamlessly exchange, interpret, and use data across different platforms and domains. This involves ensuring that data is consistently understood and processed, regardless of the technologies or languages used to generate or consume it.
Knowledge Elicitation	The systematic process of gathering, organizing, and negotiating knowledge with domain experts to create a structured representation of a specific domain's concepts, relationships, and semantics.
Linked Data	A set of best practices for publishing, sharing, and interlinking structured data on the web in a way that is machine-readable, interoperable, and easily connected with other data. Linked Data is the foundation of the Semantic Web, enabling the integration and reuse of data across different sources.
Material Culture	Field of study that analyzes the interactions between tangible entities and human beings.
Natural Heritage	Any form of Heritage that is not directly created by humans.
Ontology	A structured framework used to model a knowledge domain: using logical relationships, ontologies support reasoning and inference, enabling the extraction of new knowledge based on encoded concepts, relationships, and rules.
Ontology Engineering	The process of creating and maintaining an ontology, encompassing activities such as the development process, lifecycle management, and the application of specific methodologies, tools, and languages to build an interoperable, logically consistent representation of a domain.
Resource Description Framework (RDF)	A framework for representing information about resources in the web. It provides a standard way to describe relationships between resources

using triples (subject-predicate-object) and enables the creation of a graph of interconnected data. It does not impose any structure or semantics beyond the basic triple format.

Resource Description Framework Schema (RDFS)

Extends RDF and provides mechanisms to describe the relationships between classes and properties. It defines a way to create hierarchies between them, allowing users to specify relationships like subclassing and property types. Enables reasoning about data, such as inferring that if A is a subclass of B, then any instance of A is also an instance of B.

Semantic Artefact

An interoperable, machine- and human-readable formalization of a given domain, encompassing everything from controlled vocabularies to logically consistent ontologies.

Tangible Entity

Any entity perceivable by humans with the sense of touch.

Tangible Heritage

Any form of Heritage represented by a tangible entity.

Use case

Structured description of how a system, product, or service responds to actions initiated by an external actor—such as a user or another system—to achieve a specific goal.

VERSIONING & CONTRIBUTION HISTORY

Version	Date	Description	Authors	Comments
1.0	31-10-2024	Parts I-II	Irene Rossi, Erica Scarpa, Riccardo Valente	Initial draft completed and submitted
1.0	31-10-2024	Annex	Alberto Bucciero, Alessandra Chirivì, Matteo Greco, Andrea Pandurino	Initial draft completed and submitted

INTRODUCTION AND SCOPE

The Humanities and Cultural Heritage Open Science Cloud (H2IOSC) is a project coordinated by the Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR), with active participation from several of its institutes (<https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it/>). The project's primary goal is to establish a federated and inclusive cluster of Italian nodes for four European Research Infrastructures (RIs) focused on the Humanities and Cultural Heritage: DARIAH for digital humanities, CLARIN for language sciences, OPERAS for scholarly communication in the Humanities and Social Sciences, and E-RIHS for Heritage Science. These RIs vary significantly, encompassing physical instruments, archives, databases, and essential computing and communication systems that support research.

The overarching mission of H2IOSC is to advance data-driven research and drive the digital transformation of the cultural and creative sectors. It promotes a data-centric model, where information is made accessible via an integrated digital environment aligned with Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016).

The Institute of Heritage Science (CNR-ISPC) plays a crucial role in the project as part of the E-RIHS network (<https://www.e-rihs.it/>). Specifically, the ISPC Milan branch leads Task 4.10, titled 'Resources Interoperability: DIGILAB Resources (E-RIHS)' within Work Package 4 (WP4), which focuses on ensuring interoperability among RIs nodes and resources. Task 4.10 is a pivotal element of WP4, concentrating on achieving seamless interoperability between resources hosted on the DIGILAB platform, which will serve as a hub for data exchange, virtual research, and collaboration in the Heritage field. The present deliverable addresses the main objectives of Task 4.10, namely:

1. Mapping formats, standards, and ontologies used in the fields of Cultural Heritage and Heritage Science.
2. Designing an ontology for the Heritage Science domain.
3. Ensuring compatibility of formats and strategies for cross-domain integration.
4. Supporting the interoperability of the Pilots developed in WP7.

Specifically, the Milan branch of ISPC conducted research aiming at defining the scope of both the objectives #1 and #2, which is that of Heritage Science, as illustrated in detail in [Part I - Heritage: An Introduction](#). The surpassing of the dichotomy between Cultural Heritage and Heritage Science is the result of theoretical discussion detailed therein. The Milan branch carried out the mapping of existing semantic artefacts in the field of Heritage (#1), as detailed in [Mapping Semantic Resources: The Heritage – Semantic Tools and Interoperability Survey \(H-SeTIS\) Database](#). These two undertakings are the foundation for the development of an ontology tailored for the field of Heritage Science (#2), documented in [Developing an Ontology for Heritage Science](#) and described in [Heritage Science Ontology: Classes and Properties Specification](#). Particular attention has been devoted to ensuring compatibility with existing standards (#3), the most important being the CIDOC CRM ([The CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model](#)).

The Annex, edited by the Lecce branch of ISPC, aims at further documenting the support for interoperability standards for the WP7 Pilots (#4). This is preliminarily outlined in the description of the Illuminated Manuscript Ontology pilot use case (1.2 The Illuminated Manuscripts Pilot) and its Diagnostic Investigation ontology extension. The complete ontology will be fully detailed in the deliverables for WP3 and WP7.

PART I - HERITAGE: AN INTRODUCTION

Summary Building an ontology for Heritage Science (HS) primarily requires defining its field of application. Being Heritage a rich and complex concept intertwined with many aspects of human life, the following paragraphs will explore the main theories revolving around the conceptualization of this domain. Paragraph 1 offers a short presentation of HS, which is also the specific domain for the ontology being modeled in the project. Paragraph 2 addresses the wide and complex topic of Heritage, detailing various relevant aspects related to it. Subparagraph 2.1.1 explores the concept of Culture as formalized during the last centuries by anthropology. The presentation of the main theoretical approaches to Culture helps to situate Heritage within a broader framework, tackling issues such as the creation of Culture, its processes and its role. Subparagraph 2.1.2 outlines the meaning and main official definitions of Cultural Heritage (CH).

Subparagraph 2.2.1 highlights a brief outline of Nature, with the main common and divergent aspects it has with human beings (subparagraph 2.2.2). Additionally, Natural Heritage (NH) is defined: while NH still plays a minor role in HS, it is essential for appreciating and contextualizing the evolving boundaries of Heritage in recent times.

Subparagraphs 2.3.1 and 2.3.2 present the concepts and main definitions of Tangible Heritage (TH) and Intangible Heritage (IH) respectively, considering the fundamental influence of human perception. An additional subparagraph (2.3.3) outlines the main features of Material Culture (MC), a field of study dealing with both the tangible and intangible aspects of human life. Closely related to archaeology and anthropology, MC offers fresh and unique perspectives on the tangible world surrounding human beings.

While the previous paragraphs of Part I are basically a state of the art of existent theoretical approaches to Heritage and Culture, the last paragraph presents the theoretical assumptions stemming from the previous reasoning, on which the HS ontology presented in Part II is based.

1 WHAT HERITAGE SCIENCE IS

HS is an interdisciplinary research field combining social and natural sciences and Humanities applied to CH and NH. While its scope and objectives are well established, the formal recognition of HS as an independent sector is still in progress. This definition of HS was jointly formulated in 2019 by the European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (E-RIHS) infrastructure and the International Centre for the Study of the Preservation and Restoration of Cultural Property (ICCROM)¹. The term itself was coined by the Science and Technology Select Committee of the British House of Lords in 2006 (Lords Science and Technology Select Committee 2006; Kennedy 2015, 214–15; Strlič 2018, 7260; Kennedy et al. 2024). This new definition seeks to bridge disciplinary divides, particularly between Cultural Heritage Conservation—which has traditionally emphasized the technical aspects of assessing and managing degradation, restoration, and safeguarding tangible Cultural Heritage—and the social sciences, which explore material evidence and their relationships between humans and the environment through disciplines like archaeology, art history, and anthropology (Carman and Stig Sørensen 2009).

In recent decades, advancements in scientific techniques for remote sensed data have significantly enhanced the analytical capabilities and applications of HS diagnostic methodologies. This improvement is particularly relevant given the fragility of materials studied, which often limited more invasive interventions and direct sampling. The ability to gather data without direct contact has broadened the range of measurements and research areas, resulting in improved scientific outcomes (Kennedy 2015, 220–21).

The establishment of HS as a domain aims to shift the emphasis from individual disciplines, each with its unique characteristics, to a focus on the research object, *i.e.* the ‘Heritage’. This shift fosters greater collaboration among researchers and enhances contextual understanding beyond isolated research

¹ <https://www.e-rihs.eu/e-rihs-in-a-nutshell/> (last visit 10-10-2024).

projects, facilitating cooperation across diverse areas of expertise and a more coordinated approach. Several authors have highlighted the necessity for shared data repositories and effective management tools (Kennedy 2015, 224–25; Bordalo, Bottaini, and Candeias 2021; Castelli, Felicetti, and Proietti 2021). Although this need is common across the scientific community, it is especially critical in HS due to the complex nature of potential research fields and its multidisciplinary character.

2 WHAT HERITAGE IS

Like many concepts delineated by human beings, the meaning and characteristics of Heritage have evolved over the centuries and vary depending on local cultures. The English term derives from Old French, which in turn comes from Latin, and essentially means ‘what it deserves to be transmitted to heirs’ (Harrison 2020, 42–43). Neither the values nor the characteristics on which this definition is grounded are explicitly described. One might assume that the intention to preserve something for future generations due to its importance is a common trait among human beings. However, the identification of a specific moment in history, supported by evidence, when this happened is a more challenging task. Similarly, understanding whether ‘practical’ needs arose before, after, or simultaneously with ‘spiritual’ needs poses significant difficulties.

All ancient complex societies show clear examples of the presence of Heritage practices. Despite this, the origins of Heritage as currently intended by Heritage Studies are usually traced to more recent times. The Enlightenment in Europe, characterized by scientific advancements and a neat break with a long-lasting past, is considered the period when the concept of Heritage started to take shape in its modern form. The continuous expansion of geographical horizons through discoveries and military conquests brought previously unknown cultures into direct contact with one another. The further industrialization occurred in 19th century, the rise of Romanticism and nationalism, the spread of Darwinian theories, significantly influenced the concept of Heritage. On one hand, these events helped the construction of national and personal identities, while on the other hand they increasingly contributed to consider nature as part of the Heritage, especially in northern Europe where monumental traces of the past were less numerous or distinguishable (Harrison 2020, 43–52).

In the 20th century, the two World Wars resulted in widespread destruction of monumental and TH on an unprecedented scale. The pursuit of a global agreement that could prevent or mitigate the impact of armed conflicts also influenced the perception of Heritage, culminating in the creation of UNESCO in 1945. The worldwide impact of UNESCO is exemplified by its significant activities concerning Cultural Heritage, such as the salvages of Egyptian temples threatened by the construction of dams on the Nile River. UNESCO contributed over the years to create an idea of a global and shared Heritage, culminating in 1972 with the creation of the World Heritage and World Heritage Sites.

Several studies highlight how the UNESCO approach to Heritage suffers of two main biases, *i.e.* a Western-centered perspective that does not consider enough those variations on the concept of Heritage present in different cultures—in evident contrast with its global purposes—and an excessive focus on material and even monumental evidence that, again, does not always represent the variety of human cultures (Harrison 2020, 52–59). The further expansion in 2003 of UNESCO to IH (see paragraph [What Intangible Heritage is](#)) is interpreted by some scholar as an attempt to rectify the previous exclusions and embrace perspectives on Heritage different from the Western viewpoint.

Throughout the 20th century, particularly in its final decades and into the early 21st century, contemporary societies entered in what is called post-modernity or late-modernity, as defined by anthropologists and sociologists. An advanced economic and partially social globalization, the adoption of post-capitalistic economic models, the pervasiveness of advanced digital technology, the impact of urban sprawl and of military or terrorist destruction, a different perception of time related to quick technological advancements and disruptions, have all contributed to the common impression of the past as characterized by steadiness and reassuring values. This brought to a quick increase of Heritage both in its theoretical definitions and in its real presence in everyday life; the raise of mass

tourism industry and the so-called experience economy only strengthened the changes in Heritage perception and role in contemporary societies (Harrison 2020, 63–86).

Alternative or adjacent definitions of Heritage often coexist, as its meaning progressively shifts due to socio-cultural changes. In recent decades, Heritage has increasingly been defined by the relations that exist among human beings, material things, environment and other individuals. For instance, for Smith (2010, 11) «Heritage is therefore ultimately a cultural practice, involved in the construction and regulation of a range of values and understandings». However, it must be stressed that a complete and harmonized definition of Heritage is still lacking, at least at a national level (Ahmad 2006).

2.1 THE CULTURAL SIDE

Summary Culture is an essential trait of human beings. It is shared across all human groups yet remains distinct from one group to another. Culture has always been considered exclusive to humans: although this perspective has slightly changed over the 20th century, it is still perceived as typically human. Every form of Culture is in some way a form of Heritage, because it is transmitted over time. However, while certain aspects are inherited unintentionally, others are deliberately selected to be preserved and passed down through time.

2.1.1 What Culture is²

The term ‘Culture’ has at least two main meanings that have emerged over time. Traditionally, ‘Culture’ is the sum of knowledge and skills obtained through education and study, often attributed to single individuals. In a more modern sense, Culture denotes the sum of characteristics and behaviors that denote a social group.

The concept of ‘Culture’ began emerging in the 18th century, shaped by social revolutions, scientific progress, and new geographic explorations. Voltaire was one of the first to address Culture in his *Essai sur les mœurs* (1756), contrasting Nature’s homogeneity with Culture’s heterogeneity. Later, Johann Gottfried Herder broadened Culture’s scope to encompass all human activities, not just intellectual pursuits. This broader view continued with Gustave Klemm, who described Culture as “essential” in history, signaling a shift from an elitist view of Culture toward a more inclusive perspective.

Edward B. Tylor formalized Culture as a universal, acquired, and socially bound “complex whole” encompassing knowledge, beliefs, customs, and skills. Tylor’s work distinguished Culture from genetic inheritance and emphasized its connection to society. As **variations** in human Culture happen at a relative high speed, this clearly differentiates humans from animals, whose major biological changes take place at a much slower pace. Artifacts and language serve as essential aspects of Culture, extending physical and intellectual capabilities and enabling social connection. Language, especially, embodies Culture’s symbolic nature and its relationship with human consciousness—a point debated by scholars such as Marx, Engels, and Kroeber, who affirmed that Culture succeeds organic nature as it coincides with different stages in human evolution.

In the 20th century, thinkers like Clifford Geertz and Roger Keesing emphasized Culture as something external to, yet inseparable from, the organic layer of humanity. The concept evolved to focus on the diversity of cultural practices, which were previously seen as merely fleeting traditions. Palaeontologic discoveries during the 20th century further suggested that Culture and human biology co-evolved. André Leroi-Gourhan proposed that bipedalism was a driving factor in the development of language and cognitive skills: the revolutionary consequence is that the brain and its evolution are a product of Culture and there is a circular and seamless influence between Culture and the human organism (interactive model). Culture is not limited to technology and MC (see paragraph [What Material Culture is](#)) but extends to symbolism. According to Bronisław K. Malinowski, the relevant position of symbolism in Culture does not exclude that one of its main aims is to answer to biological needs: even

² This paragraph is largely drawn on Remotti (1992) also when not explicitly expressed.

MC needs a symbolic framework and biological needs have cultural, *i.e.* symbolically organized answers.

Culture inherently carries **precariousness**, as it depends on continuous social reconstruction and adaptability for its survival. This precariousness fosters **variation**, through which Culture is realized and transmitted. However, cultural variations are typically limited in range, as they contribute to the general characteristics of a certain Culture. Along with variation, **selection** is another key concept for Culture, because it is through selection that practices and symbols are chosen, often at the expense of others. This selective process lays the groundwork for another typical trait of Culture, which is **peculiarity**. Every Culture is distinct because it results from the selection of a vast array of possible characteristics. Yet this selection is never final, but is as precarious as Culture itself, meaning that future changes are always possible.

2.1.2 What Cultural Heritage is

Cultural Heritage is probably the most common and popular kind of Heritage. The term refers, as previously stated, to any form of Heritage that is created by human beings. Cultural Heritage was largely defined by national and international rules, that evolved over time along with the evolution of Heritage itself.

The first official definition of Heritage appears in the 'Final act of the Intergovernmental Conference on the Protection of Cultural Property in the Event of Armed Conflict' held in The Hague in 1954 (Hague 1954). The act appears to distinguish between 'Cultural Heritage' (that is called within the text also 'patrimonio cultural' in Spanish, 'patrimoine culturel' in French, 'культурного наследия' in Russian) and 'Cultural Property' ('bienes culturales', 'biens culturels', 'культурным ценностям'). Article 1 provides the definition of Cultural Property, encompassing «movable or immovable property of great importance to the cultural heritage of every people», including «monuments of architecture, art or history, (...) archaeological sites, groups of buildings (...), works of art, manuscripts, books and other objects of artistic, historical or archaeological interest, (...) scientific collections and important collections of books or archives»³.

The 'International Charter for the Conservation and Restoration of Monuments and Sites' (also known as The Venice Charter) issued in 1964 in Venice principally focused on the architectural Heritage⁴.

The concept of Cultural Property that models the Cultural Heritage of a nation is kept also in the 'Convention on the Means of Prohibiting and Preventing the Illicit Import, Export and Transfer of Ownership of Cultural Property' held in Paris in 1970 that better details the components of Cultural Property in art. 1⁵.

³ Art. 1: «For the purposes of the present Convention, the term "cultural property" shall cover, irrespective of origin or ownership: - monuments: architectural works, works of monumental sculpture and painting, elements or structures of an archaeological nature, inscriptions, cave dwellings and combinations of features, which are of outstanding universal value from the point of view of history, art or science; - groups of buildings: groups of separate or connected buildings which, because of their architecture, their homogeneity or their place in the landscape, are of outstanding universal value from the point of view of history, art or science; - sites: works of man or the combined works of nature and of man, and areas including archaeological sites which are of outstanding universal value from the historical, aesthetic, ethnological or anthropological points of view».

⁴ Art. 1: «The concept of a historic monument embraces not only the single architectural work but also the urban or rural setting in which is found the evidence of a particular civilization, a significant development or a historic event. This applies not only to great works of art but also to more modest works of the past which have acquired cultural significance with the passing of time».

⁵ Art. 1: «For the purposes of this Convention, the term "cultural property" means property which, on religious or secular grounds, is specifically designated by each State as being of importance for archaeology, prehistory, history, literature, art or science and which belongs to the following categories: (a) Rare collections and specimens of fauna, flora, minerals and anatomy, and objects of palaeontological interest; (b) Property relating to history, including the history of science and technology and military and social history, to the life of national leaders, thinkers, scientists and artist and to events of national importance; (c) Products of archaeological excavations (including regular and clandestine) or of archaeological discoveries; (d) Elements of artistic or historical monuments or archaeological sites which have been dismembered; (e) Antiquities more than one hundred years old, such as inscriptions, coins and engraved seals; (f) Objects of ethnological interest; (g) Property of artistic interest, such as: (i) pictures, paintings and drawings produced entirely by hand on any support and in any material (excluding industrial designs and manufactured articles decorated by hand); (ii) original works of statuary art and sculpture in any material; (iii) original engravings, prints and lithographs; (iv) original artistic assemblages and montages in any material; (h) Rare manuscripts

The 1972 'Convention concerning the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage' which lead to the creation of the UNESCO World Heritage, seems to abandon the concept of 'Cultural Property' to focus only on Cultural Heritage ('patrimonio cultural' in Spanish, 'patrimoine culturel' in French, 'культурного наследия' in Russian, 'التراث الثقافي' in Arabic). However, the convention essentially repeats most of the elements that were already part of Heritage as defined by the previous Conventions⁶.

As far as Italy is concerned, the most recent definition of Cultural Heritage is included in the "Codice per i Beni Culturali" (D.L. 2004/42): Art. 2 specifies that cultural assets are «(...) those movable and not movable assets that, according to articles 10 and 11, have an artistic, historical, archaeological, ethno-anthropological, archival and bibliographic value, and those other assets that rules acknowledge as evidence of civilization»⁷.

2.2 THE NATURAL SIDE

Summary While Culture has often been associated with human creations, Nature is what is not directly created by humans, as well as being the primary environment in which they live and act. From this perspective, Nature inevitably contrasts with Culture in more or less accentuated ways. Nevertheless, a NH undeniably exists and has a role in the wider Heritage discourse.

2.2.1 What Nature is

The term Nature changes its meaning «(...) as our scientific conception of the world changes, and [is] often best seen as signifying a contrast with something considered not part of nature» (Blackburn 2008). Nature was considered by ancient Greeks as the whole universe, encompassing every entity that emerges and undergoes change. Much of this meaning can be somehow valid today, often referring to, and implicitly contrasting with, Nature as the whole not created by human beings. Origins of this juxtaposition go back to Plato, Aristotle and the Cynics. During the Middle Ages, Nature is the product of God's creation, considered inferior to humans: this view shifted during the Renaissance, when Nature is seen as sharing the same divine spirit characterizing humans. But during the same period a different perception arises: Nature responds to universal laws that are well understandable using the language of Math and Geometry (mechanistic approach). From the Enlightenment onward, changes in the concept of Nature occurred at a much quicker pace. The Enlightenment considered Nature as clearly opposed to human civilization but also as a model for human behavior. In contrast, Romanticism saw in Nature the presence of a greater Spirit and divine essence. Positivism in 19th and the beginning of 20th centuries pushed Nature into the background of technological progress, suggesting that humanity, after centuries of struggle and subjugation, could finally dominate it completely (Treccani 2009).

2.2.2 What Natural Heritage is

Interest for NH emerged somewhat later than that for CH, around the second half of 19th century (Lowenthal and Olwig 2006, 81). In Europe, the recognition of NH varied significantly by country. For instance, in north-European countries NH was regarded as a more pervasive presence than CH

and incunabula, old books, documents and publications of special interest (historical, artistic, scientific, literary, etc.) singly or in collections; (i) Postage, revenue and similar stamps, singly or in collections; (j) Archives, including sound, photographic and cinematographic archives; (k) Articles of furniture more than one hundred years old and old musical instruments».

⁶ Art. 1: «For the purposes of this Convention, the following shall be considered as "cultural heritage": - monuments : architectural works, works of monumental sculpture and painting, elements or structures of an archaeological nature, inscriptions, cave dwellings and combinations of features, which are of outstanding universal value from the point of view of history, art or science; - groups of buildings: groups of separate or connected buildings which, because of their architecture, their homogeneity or their place in the landscape, are of outstanding universal value from the point of view of history, art or science ; - sites: works of man or the combined works of nature and of man, and areas including archaeological sites which are of outstanding universal value from the historical, aesthetic, ethnological or anthropological points of view.»

⁷ Codice 2004; English translation by the autor.

compared to some south-European nations; in certain cases, the very essence of specific natural features was even contested (Sundin 2006, 8). The first national park, the Yellowstone National Park, was established in the USA in 1872, followed by the Royal National Park in Sydney in 1879 (Harrison 2020, 45).

The 1972 UNESCO Convention provided also a definition of NH ('patrimonio natural' in Spanish, 'patrimoine naturel' in French, 'природного наследия' in Russian, 'التراث الطبيعي' in Arabic) that includes «(...) natural features consisting of physical and biological formations, (...) geological and physiographical formations (...), natural sites (...)»⁸.

There are several reasons to consider NH as distinct from CH: Nature precedes human history, and its 'assets' are largely immovable. Its preservation focuses more on species and ecosystems rather than individual examples of life forms, which contrasts with the CH approach. Nevertheless, there are also common aspects between NH and CH: Nature and Culture are strictly intertwined, making it challenging to delineate clear boundaries between the two (Lowenthal and Olwig 2006, 84–87).

2.3 TANGIBLE AND INTANGIBLE

Summary The external world is perceived by human beings through their senses. Touch is a fundamental sense that helps to interact with material entities, to explore and manipulate them, and to receive a feeling of stability and duration. The possibility of being touched or not is a feature that is often used in Heritage Studies to define and manage Heritage. The main approaches and their consequences are here presented and discussed.

2.3.1 What Tangible Heritage is

TH is likely the first form of Heritage that comes to mind: a painting, a statue, a building, an epigraph—all are examples of TH. Being 'tangible' refers to the property of a given entity to be perceived by human senses, primarily and especially through the sense of touch. There are several hypotheses on why TH was the first kind of Heritage to be formally codified, many of which relate to the unique ways humans perceive and interact with the world. Touch as a sense can be defined in multiple ways but it seems to be intimately connected with agency and spatial awareness. The contact with a tangible feature reacts against our agency, giving us «(...) a more solid epistemic foundation» of reality. Another view considers that most of the information conveyed by touch, except for hot and cold, are perceived as spatial properties of objects (Fulkerson 2024). Touch ultimately serves the scope of building a sort of 'reliability map' that guides humans through the world. Many tangible things, with care and preservation, can endure far beyond a human lifespan and undergo change at a different pace. Their persistence through the world increases their perceived reliability conveying an impression of stability (Hodder 2012, 7).

2.3.2 What Intangible Heritage is

If TH is characterized by its tangibility, *i.e.* its perception by humans through touch, IH is the opposite. In the case of IH touch is not involved at all, while other senses, with hearing in a preeminent position, are privileged. The 2003 UNESCO 'Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage' held in Paris defined IH as «practices, representations, expressions, knowledge, skills – as well as the instruments, objects, artefacts and cultural spaces associated therewith – that communities, groups

⁸ Art. 2: «For the purposes of this Convention, the following shall be considered as "natural heritage": -natural features consisting of physical and biological formations or groups of such formations, which are of outstanding universal value from the aesthetic or scientific point of view; -geological and physiographical formations and precisely delineated areas which constitute the habitat of threatened species of animals and plants of outstanding universal value from the point of view of science or conservation; -natural sites or precisely delineated natural areas of outstanding universal value from the point of view of science, conservation or natural beauty.»

and, in some cases, individuals recognize as part of their cultural heritage» (Art. 2, subsections 1 and 2; “Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage”; UNESCO 2003b)⁹.

In 2003 UNESCO also issued a ‘Charter on the Preservation of Digital Heritage’ (UNESCO 2003a). As most of the digital contents are stored on tangible supports but the electromagnetic medium can be largely considered as intangible, Digital Heritage (DH) can be reasonably included into the larger field of IH. The Charter states that DH includes «(...) texts, databases, still and moving images, audio, graphics, software and web pages, among a wide and growing range of formats»¹⁰.

The inclusion of IH as part of the UNESCO’s World Heritage sought to address an imbalance in Heritage representation, which had traditionally favored civilizations with visible, monumental artifacts. Despite this effort, the separation of Heritage between tangible and intangible is still debated. Some scholars argue that indigenous ontologies—in the philosophical sense of the term, referring to the concepts of reality held by indigenous peoples—offer different perspectives about the concept of Heritage where boundaries between nature, culture, tangible and intangible are not relevant, as everything is intertwined: «Rather than imagining a process by which human meaning makers engage in heritage practices by making meanings in or through physical realities, we are rather pushed to imagine that humans and other sentient beings bind time collaboratively » (Harrison and Rose 2010, 266).

2.3.3 What Material Culture is

MC is a multidisciplinary field of study that primarily involves Archaeology and Anthropology, Sociology and Philosophy (Berger 2009; Olsen 2010, 21). Wider applications can be found in social and behavioral studies and psychological sciences (Buse and Twigg 2014); to analyze complex social phenomena (De León 2012) and historical events (Saunders 2004); for marketing research (Garnier 2013); in psychiatry (Parrott 2010); in architecture (Macdonald 2006). MC was even applied to ethological studies which involve animals such as great apes (Van Schaik et al. 2003).

As with any theoretical framework, MC theories are influenced by wider socio-cultural contexts. As Marxism influenced archaeology and history, during the second half of 19th century a renewed focus was set on historical objects: their production methods and the effects produced on social organization were a core topic of Marx’s theories (Dei and Meloni 2015, 38–39). This focus on objects can be also considered a consequence of mass production and mass-media culture that started to develop after the industrial revolution (Hamling and Richardson 2010, 4). Moreover, the Marxist approach, which deeply influenced archaeological theories during the whole 20th century (Renfrew and Bahn 2012, 471–73) and was in turn influenced by Darwin’s ideas on evolution, helped to better consider evidence from the past that was previously neglected due to being expressions of ordinary

⁹ Art. 2: «For the purposes of this Convention, 1. The “intangible cultural heritage” means the practices, representations, expressions, knowledge, skills – as well as the instruments, objects, artefacts and cultural spaces associated therewith – that communities, groups and, in some cases, individuals recognize as part of their cultural heritage. This intangible cultural heritage, transmitted from generation to generation, is constantly recreated by communities and groups in response to their environment, their interaction with nature and their history, and provides them with a sense of identity and continuity, thus promoting respect for cultural diversity and human creativity. For the purposes of this Convention, consideration will be given solely to such intangible cultural heritage as is compatible with existing international human rights instruments, as well as with the requirements of mutual respect among communities, groups and individuals, and of sustainable development. 2. The “intangible cultural heritage”, as defined in paragraph 1 above, is manifested inter alia in the following domains: (a) oral traditions and expressions, including language as a vehicle of the intangible cultural heritage; (b) performing arts; (c) social practices, rituals and festive events; (d) knowledge and practices concerning nature and the universe; (e) traditional craftsmanship».

¹⁰ Art. 1: «The digital heritage consists of unique resources of human knowledge and expression. It embraces cultural, educational, scientific and administrative resources, as well as technical, legal, medical and other kinds of information created digitally, or converted into digital form from existing analogue resources. Where resources are “born digital”, there is no other format but the digital object. Digital materials include texts, databases, still and moving images, audio, graphics, software and web pages, among a wide and growing range of formats. They are frequently ephemeral, and require purposeful production, maintenance and management to be retained. Many of these resources have lasting value and significance, and therefore constitute a heritage that should be protected and preserved for current and future generations. This ever-growing heritage may exist in any language, in any part of the world, and in any area of human knowledge or expression».

people. This new approach was strengthened during the 20th century with the French school of the *Annales* (Burke 1992).

Definitions can be various. For instance, MC has been defined as:

«(...) a term used to describe the objects produced by human beings, including buildings, structures, monuments, tools, weapons, utensils, furniture, art, and indeed any physical item created by a society. (...) A distinction is often made between those aspects of culture that appear as physical objects and those aspects that are non-material» (Darvill 2002, 250–51).

Another definition states that MC includes:

«(...) the artifacts and ecofacts used by a group to cope with the physical and social environment. (...) The distinction is made between those aspects of culture that appear as physical object and those aspects that are nonmaterial. It is the major source of evidence for archaeology» (Kipfer 2000, 338).

A strict comparison, if not a complete overlapping, of MC with TH could be drawn considering these definitions. A clear distinction is established between MC, which is notably tangible, and other aspects of reality that are 'nonmaterial'. The second definition opens the realm of MC also to 'ecofacts', *i.e.* «non-artifactual organic and environmental remains» (Renfrew and Bahn 2012, 50) such as human and animal bones, pollens, charcoals that are sometimes only indirect markers of human activities. However, other definitions help to widen the concept and enrich it. For instance, in Orser (2002, 339–42) MC is defined as:

«that sector of our physical environment that we modify through culturally modified behavior. (...) Some archaeologists broaden the concept of material culture even further and contend that facial make-up, fingerprints and even body odours constitute examples of material culture».

Here the concept of MC expands to the physical world surrounding humans. Nevertheless, some scholars do not limit the extent of MC only to the tangible world. For instance, Prown (1982, 1) states that MC «(...) is the study through artifacts of the beliefs-values, ideas, attitudes, and assumptions of a particular community or society at a given time». Here the shift from a matter-centered approach to a much wider one is evident. For Giannichedda (2009, 101–2) the MC «(...) of every social group can be considered as composed by the totality of artefacts, by practices aimed to produce, exchange, use, break, discard them and by attributions of meaning relative both to artifacts and their use». An intricate and complex web of relationships entangles human beings and things (Hodder 2012). Despite this, focusing only on aspects more connected to the production of material artifacts belonging to MC reveals that technology has an undoubted immaterial component which comprises knowledge, skills, experience, and habits (Eglash 2006).

2.4 FADING BOUNDARIES: THE CONCEPT OF LANDSCAPE

Landscape is a good example of how it can be difficult to draw clear lines between NH and CH, as well as between TH and IH. In Europe, the idea that Landscape—at least certain types of Landscape—can be considered as CH emerged at the beginning of the 20th century. Geographer Otto Schlüter is credited with coining the term 'Kulturlandschaft' ('Cultural Landscape') to describe the deep visible changes made by humans in the 'Urlandschaft' ('original Landscape') (Hofmeister 2004, 4). The concept was further developed by Sauer (1963, 321, 343) who stated that «(...) culture is the agent, the natural area is the medium, the cultural landscape is the result». However, some scholars radically changed the paradigm of analysis. According to Cosgrove (1998, 1), landscape is «a way of seeing», an epistemology that has symbolic dimension; Landscape can be viewed as a «discourse materialized» or «the tangible (...) articulations of numerous discourses» (Daniels 1989). From these assumptions, Landscape tends to have a dual material and immaterial character (Cosgrove and Daniels 1988, 1, 8).

UNESCO recognized 'cultural landscapes' in 1992 with the 'Revision of the Operational Guidelines for the Implementation of the World Heritage Convention' (UNESCO 1992, art. 3, subclause c) acknowledging them as part of the "combined works of nature and man" mentioned in Art. 1 of the

1972 Convention. The Art. 131 of the Italian 'Codice dei beni culturali e del paesaggio' defines Landscape as «(...) a territory that expresses identity, whose character arises from the interplay of natural and human factors and their interrelationships»¹¹.

3 THEORETICAL ASSUMPTIONS FOR A HERITAGE SCIENCE ONTOLOGY

The previous paragraphs tried to briefly outline the concepts of Heritage and its various specification. It is evident that Heritage, Culture and Nature are interrelated concepts that evolve over time according to historical events, social dynamics, and economic and technological turns.

As far as Europe is concerned, Culture was traditionally understood as the enhancement of personal skills and knowledge. During the 18th century, the Enlightenment opposed Culture, as a typical human trait, to everything that was 'natural'. During this phase, Heritage is largely cultural, characterized by monumentality and exceptional nature. During the 19th century, the industrial revolution, geographic explorations, and political philosophies such as Marxism, as well as biological theories such as Darwinism, brought to a progressive redefinition of Culture. This redefinition encompassed everything that is learned and transmitted within a social group, considering culture as a development that follows organic nature as a result of evolution. Heritage is still largely material, with a renewed focus on objects and production processes, while also playing a significant role in the construction of national identities. During the end of the 19th century and the first half of the 20th century the concept of Culture was deeply influenced by anthropology, which emphasized the close interconnection between culture and human biology. Anthropology recognized the existence of a form of Culture in every human group and defined the processes of its transmission and selection. In the second half of the 20th century, after the two World Wars, globalization, technological advancements and evolving capitalistic models brought to a progressive expansion of the concept of Heritage, which included also immaterial evidence, making Heritage a global business. The definitive emergence of the Information Age, characterized by digital data and tools, further expanded the boundaries of Culture and Heritage, pushing them into uncharted territories.

While advancing the definitions of Heritage is not the primary aim of this work, establishing a foundational discourse on the topic and related concepts is essential for the objectives of Task 4.10. Building a semantic web ontology requires, among other things, a deep knowledge of the target domain and the establishment of clear domain boundaries. The main challenge in developing the Heritage Science Ontology is twofold: its scope can change in response to sociocultural modifications over time, and its boundaries are as broad as the diversity of human experience. Before diving into the details, it is important to note that the theoretical assumptions presented in the last paragraph of Part I are a form of cultural expression themselves, and are inevitably affected by the background, knowledge, skills, and the belonging to a certain historical period and culture of its authors. As a result, these assumptions may contain biases that limit its validity. Moreover, some topics treated here do not have a single accepted formalization but encompass multiple definitions and theories that reflect different perspectives and at the same time contribute to a broader, evolving definition.

To address both the theoretical and technological needs, certain choices were made that shape the entire ontology. Based on recent scientific theories and discussions, the decision was made to move beyond the alleged Cartesian dualism between Nature and Culture, deeply rooted in the Western approach to Heritage. While Descartes himself probably did not advocate for a complete separation between mind and body, and while this separation may still serve practical purposes in Heritage management (a marble statue is not an animal species), there are compelling reasons to adopt an integrated perspective. For instance, consider the following example: a plant is inherently natural. A plant that is selected for its colors to be part of a decorative garden pattern remains natural but is

¹¹ Codice 2004; English translation by the author.

used in a cultural way. Conversely, a plant whose colors are the result of grafting and selective breeding is *relevantly* cultural. A plant that in a hypothetical future would be result of genetic modifications so invasive to result in a new species would be *largely*, if not totally, cultural.

A real life example is the *Vanda falcata*, commonly known as the “samurai orchid,” which exemplifies the intricate relationship between nature and culture (Fig.3.1). Native to Japan and popular during the Edo period (1603-1868), this orchid was cherished not only for its beauty but also as a symbol of elegance and wealth. Specimens with distinctive leaves or flowers became known as *fūkiran*, literally “orchid of wealth and nobility.” Some *fūkiran* are so unique that they are regarded as a form of art (Schiff 2018, 6), regardless of its aesthetical appearance.

Fig. 3.1: Samurai orchids on display at a local exhibition.

Overcoming the division between nature and culture implicitly suggests a perspective in which everything can be viewed as ‘human-interpreted’ (cultural), a debated and sometimes criticized stance known as Constructivism. The human tendency to overlay everything with a cultural layer strongly supports this perspective. This opinion is implicitly acknowledged in the opening of this section, where it is suggested that the opinions and models presented here are also forms of culture influenced by other cultural contexts. Nevertheless, some further considerations must be framed within the actual scope of this work. The constructivist approach can help maintaining the momentum of the progressive and ongoing expansion of the concept of Heritage that occurred during the 20th century, and it will be partially preserved. However, it presents a relevant challenge with reference to a semantic web ontology, as the need for clear delimitation of the domain often conflicts with potentially endless realms of interpretation and application. Another point is that the terms ‘Culture’ and ‘cultural’ themselves experienced, like Heritage, an expansion of their boundaries. If Culture stopped to represent the traditional human ‘habits and traditions’ and started to define those processes and relations that are transmitted within social groups and sometimes embodied in tangible entities (MC), it has also been applied in ethological contexts, especially concerning primates (Mainardi 1974). The issues related to a strict division between NH and CH are evident also in UNESCO’s evolving approach. Art. 46 of the modified Operational Guidelines issued in 2005 introduced the category of ‘mixed cultural and natural heritage’ for those sites that «(...) satisfy a part or the whole of the definitions of both cultural and natural heritage laid out in Articles 1 and 2 of the *Convention*» (UNESCO 2005). These considerations further support the previous choice of not tracing strict limits that divide Nature from Culture.

While major museum institutions and archaeological sites worldwide are central to large part of international HS activities, building an ontology for HS considering only this part of Heritage would be inadequate. Given that heritage is a living and evolving concept, a primary challenge lies in navigating

this volatile realm. For the scope of this work, the focus is not on the values connected to Heritage and its role for human beings. However, it can be asserted that being part of the past and being exceptional are two main characteristics of Heritage. Without taking into account complex arguments surrounding Time and its three main configurations—*i.e.* past, present and future—an ontology for HS should address not only past Heritage, but also what will come to be recognized as part of “Heritage” in the future.

Some examples can help better explain these aspects. Human footprints can be considered a common feature on Earth. They are a local modification of soft soil created by the pressure of the human body—specifically, the feet—that creates a negative imprint of the lower side of the limbs engaged in walking. Typically, they are not considered valuable from any perspective, as their persistence is usually quite short as they are tied to the surface on which they are found. Despite these characteristics, a number of human footprints from the past still survives. An example can be found at Lake Managua in Nicaragua, where a group of humans walking side by side created the Acahualinca footprints (Fig.3.2), which were preserved in a field of solidified lava discovered in 1874. During the 1940s, the area was protected, and a small museum was built. Those footprints were later dated and considered to be approximately 2000 years old (Schmincke et al. 2009). Their exceptional nature here lies not in what they actually are—simple footprints—but in their antiquity and remarkable preservation. Their primary ‘cultural’ value could also be disputed, as they were unintentionally left as a result of walking: to this respect they are not particularly different from footprints left by animals, including extinct species like the dinosaurs’ footprints found in Lerici, northern Italy (Dal Sasso 2003, 46, 50). Cary Grant’s footprints (actually shoeprints) left in a concrete slab in front of the Grauman’s Chinese Theatre in 1951 are ‘more cultural’ because they were left intentionally and because they are an example of ‘planned Heritage’, something expressly created to be preserved (Fig 3.3).

Figure 3.2: the Acahualinca footprints (D Dansereau, CC BY-SA 3.0, via Wikimedia Commons)

Buzz Aldrin’s footprints (actually bootprints) left during the 1969 Apollo 11 mission on the surface of the Moon became Heritage at the moment they were created, due to their enormous symbolic meaning (Fig.3.4). However, it is likely that only photographic representations will remain as evidence of their existence. Similarly, the first bootprints on the surface of Mars or any other planet human beings will be able to reach will be, and in part already is, Heritage.

Figure 3.3: Cary Grant's footprints outside the Grauman's Chinese Theatre (Andreas Praefcke, Public domain, via Wikimedia Commons)

Figure 3.4: Buzz Aldrin's bootprint on the Moon surface (NASA/Buzz Aldrin, Public domain, via Wikimedia Commons)

Definition of Heritage for the purposes of the Project

Given these premises, it is possible to define what can be considered Heritage for the scope of this work. "Potential Heritage" encompasses *every entity, whether existing inside or outside of human beings, with which they interact at any level*. This extensive pool of entities is reduced by the introduction of a key element: the recognition of given values, implying the transmission and survival of that specific entity over others. In other words, a **selection** occurs, reducing the "potential Heritage" to a portion of it that is defined only in opposition with the "potential Heritage" itself, rather than by its specific entities.

Despite the previous statement about the overcome of the dualistic approach between Nature and Culture, a form of dualism has been retained as a theoretical assumption in the ontology here developed, specifically the distinction between the concepts of 'tangible' and 'intangible.'

This division is well rooted in Heritage Studies as well (see the UNESCO definitions in paragraphs [What Tangible Heritage is](#) and [What Intangible Heritage is](#)) and it certainly represents a partial perspective that is not universal (see the discourse on indigenous ontologies, paragraph [What Intangible Heritage is](#)). While for the purposes of this work the division between Nature and Culture is not considered

crucial and has been justified, it is important to acknowledge that Heritage is intrinsically connected to humans' perspective, influenced and oriented by their cognitive skills and their perception of the surrounding environment. While Philosophy and Physics stress the changeability of reality and even question its real existence, humans need a certain degree of stability. Though reality can be perceived through many senses, touch is the one that implicitly makes humans sure that things 'exist'. As many tangible entities are deemed persistent and durable over time, sometimes more than humans themselves, tangible elements easily convey that sense of stability over time, from past to future. While the next considerations may stem from personal experience or common sense, it appears that humans have frequently sought to transform intangible entities into tangible forms, of which writing could be one of the most relevant examples. While the juxtaposition between Nature and Culture is largely conceptual, the dichotomy between 'tangible' and 'intangible' is deeply grounded on the biology of human perception. This aspect cannot be ignored, as will keep influencing humans, at least until technological advancements can consistently render the intangible as tangible, beyond what is currently possible.

However, this juxtaposition between 'tangible' and 'intangible' is not an opposition, as relevant relations are present. Some of the international TH and IH definitions have been presented and the evolution of Heritage in relation to these concepts was assessed. Although from these institutional definitions TH and IH seem to be a bit independent in their nature and certainly in their management, they are actually deeply intertwined. While certain elements of TH, such as a statue, and IH, like a song, can be essentially independent, a significant portion of TH is often interconnected with and influences IH. Moreover, IH not only adapts to TH but also shapes and relates to it in a **mutual influence**. An example could be a given dress (TH) worn during a specific occasion, as the Korean *hwarot* which was typically worn by women during the Chosŏn period (1392–1910) for special events and weddings; the attire typically worn for certain performances (IH), as the simple garments and elaborate headdresses worn by musicians during **nongak**, a Korean folk dance (Fig.3.5). Additionally, when considering the technology and skills (intangible) used to realize tangible objects, which in turn can produce IH— for example, the Aztec death whistle (*ehēcachichtli*), an instrument designed to recreate human-screaming sounds and associated with death rituals—it becomes evident that 'tangible' and 'intangible' can be considered distinct but indivisible, something that MC studies have already well addressed.

The theoretical underpinning behind the HS ontology aims to incorporate most of the concepts related to Heritage and to adapt them in order to ensure the widest degree of flexibility and the most effective application. The concept of **selection** of entities from reality to transform them in Heritage is directly borrowed from the formalization of Culture itself, where selection acts as a fundamental defining factor. The **mutual influence** between TH and IH is directly borrowed from the MC approach and has its foundations in Cybernetics where this process is called '**feedback**'; it also applies to the anthropological interactive model of Culture that implies a feedback process between Culture and the human organism (see paragraph 2.1.1 What Culture is). A desirable outcome of considering tangible and intangible concepts as independent though strictly interconnected could be achieved with the full implementation of the HS semantic ontology, encompassing also the diagnostic analyses, where instruments could belong to the tangible side, while methods and non-material properties to the intangible side. These foundations aim to ensure that the ontology maintains a relevant operability over time, incorporating not only TH, which is still the core of HS, but also IH. This approach seeks to preserve complexity and facilitate the exploration of relationships among entities.

Fig. 3.5: (from left to right) A Korean *hwarot*; musicians performing during *nongak*; an Aztec death whistle (via Wikimedia Commons).

PART II - MODELING AN ONTOLOGY FOR THE HERITAGE FIELD

Summary The following paragraphs explore the intertwined fields of Knowledge Representation (KR) and Knowledge Engineering (KE), focusing on their objective to create systems that translate human knowledge into executable formats for machines while remaining interpretable by humans. It addresses the complexities of representing implicit expert knowledge and emphasizes the role of ontologies as structured models that define and organize concepts within specific domains. The process of Ontology Engineering (OE) is outlined, highlighting knowledge elicitation techniques, which involve systematic collaboration with domain experts.

Both knowledge representation (KR) and knowledge engineering (KE) aim to develop systems based on knowledge that is executable by machines, interpretable by humans, and capable of replicating the problem-solving abilities of a domain expert¹². Executable knowledge is thus presented in a structured, symbolic format that is clear and understandable for humans: people can read and interpret it easily, but it can also be interpreted and executed by a computer program, allowing the computer to process the information and perform problem-solving and inference tasks effectively (Peleg 2009, 1073; Kendall and McGuinness 2019, 6–7).

Since much of an expert's knowledge is implicit and tied to their skills and expertise, creating a structured representation of their specific domain is a complex undertaking. The goal of KR and KE is not to replicate the expert's cognitive processes, but rather to achieve similar outcomes in problem-solving (Studer, Benjamins, and Fensel 1998, 163). In the field of KE, ontologies are formally encoded models representing a specific knowledge domain. These models are machine-readable, logically consistent, and tailored to particular needs. Their primary purpose is to define and organize a set of concepts and the semantic relationships between them (Kendall and McGuinness 2019, 1–4)¹³. The process of creating an ontology, known as ontology engineering (OE), involves various activities, including the development process, management of lifecycle stages, and the methodologies, tools, and languages used in building the ontology (Gal 2009, 1972).

Most OE methodologies begin with **knowledge elicitation**, *i.e.*, the systematic process of gathering, organizing, and negotiating knowledge to create a structured representation of a specific domain's concepts, relationships, and semantics (Leenheer 2009). This process involves collaborating with domain experts to capture their understanding of the domain and define terms and rules that accurately represent it (Shadbolt and Smart 2015). Given the challenge of fully formalizing every concept belonging to a given domain, the goal of elicitation is to reach a consensus on key definitions and meanings through negotiation and refinement among knowledge engineers and domain experts. Knowledge elicitation in ontology development typically relies on two strategies: *top-down* approaches, which focus on acquiring knowledge directly from domain experts through interviews, case studies, and conceptual models, and *bottom-up* approaches, which employ machine learning techniques to derive patterns and relationships from large datasets (Leenheer 2009). The latter is particularly useful in large-scale data environments.

In developing an ontology for the HS domain, a top-down approach has been employed to formalize and organize the often hidden expertise of domain experts, capturing the nuanced and frequently implicit knowledge they possess. This modeling process is inherently iterative and approximate; it undergoes continuous refinement and, like all models, serves as only an approximation of reality. As discussed in Part I, the concept of Heritage has evolved over time, leading to shifts in its boundaries and core principles. In OE, new insights or observations can prompt adjustments and refinements in the model, which then inform further knowledge acquisition. Continuous evaluation and revision are essential to ensure models remains relevant and effective over time. Consequently, the ontology under development aims to address the evolving needs arising from contemporary perspectives on

¹² KR focuses on creating models and languages to formalize knowledge, while KE involves building systems that effectively use that knowledge.

¹³ For an overview of the meaning of ontology in KE, see Guarino, Oberle, and Staab 2009.

Heritage and culture, with the expectation that it will be continually improved and refined to accurately represent the domain.

A variety of methodologies exist for OE, and new approaches are regularly introduced or updated to address emerging requirements, such as those introduced by the Linked (Open) Data standard (Fernández-López and Gómez-Pérez 2002)¹⁴. Kotis, Vouros, and Spiliotopoulos (2020) classify OE methodologies as collaborative, non-collaborative, or custom, depending on the extent to which they involve a larger community of knowledge engineers and domain experts in the ontology development process. As illustrated in the following paragraphs, in the case of the Heritage Science Ontology, the Linked Open Terms (LOT) methodology (Poveda-Villalón et al. 2022) has been systematically applied whenever feasible. This approach incorporates a top-down strategy to promote a collaborative engineering process, facilitating iterative refinement, while also adhering to the latest semantic web guidelines, best practices, and ensuring compliance with FAIR principles.

4 MAPPING SEMANTIC RESOURCES: THE *HERITAGE – SEMANTIC TOOLS AND INTEROPERABILITY SURVEY* (H-SETIS) DATABASE

Summary The H-SetIS database is one of the Task 4.10's main concrete output, *i.e.* a comprehensive mapping of semantic and interoperable resources within the Heritage domain, created to enhance the documentation and organization of key resource types, including ontologies, metadata standards, thesauri, application profiles, and software. The database employs a pragmatic classification approach, allowing it to adapt to the evolving nature of these resources while adhering to FAIR principles and the Linked Open Data paradigm. A curated bibliography managed through Zotero complements the database, providing references to published materials related to semantic artifacts in the Heritage field. One of its primary objectives is to provide an overview of the current state of ontologies and semantic artifacts in the Heritage field, highlighting sub-domains of community interest. The survey also sheds light on compliance challenges with FAIR and Linked Open Data principles.

Existing aggregators of semantic artefacts do not adequately account for the multifaceted nature of the Heritage field and often fail to include artefacts that exist only at the conceptualization level¹⁵. Examples of such aggregators include the Basic Register of Thesauri, Ontologies & Classifications (BARTOC, <https://bartoc.org/>) and Linked Open Vocabularies (LOV, <https://lov.linkeddata.es/>), which rely on the semantic properties of ontologies and thesauri to display auto-generated metrics. This approach limits their scope by excluding artefacts that lack formalization in ontology-compliant languages or are highly domain-specific¹⁶.

To address these limitations, the *Heritage – Semantic Tools and Interoperability Survey* (H-SetIS) Database has been developed. Specifically created as a project output, the H-SetIS database is a comprehensive survey of semantic and interoperable resources available in the Heritage domain (Fig.4.1; Scarpa and Valente 2024–, <https://h-setis.cnr.it/>). It functions as a catalog that organizes and documents five key resource types: ontologies, metadata standards, thesauri, application profiles, and software. Each resource is described in a dedicated record according to the artefact type; the main information that are displayed are the availability date, the development status, the URI/repository and websites, the names of principal contributors and their institutions, the language (for thesauri), the used format (for ontologies), the type (for thesauri), the license, a list of keywords and the bibliographic references (Fig.4.2). Other fields show which artefacts are built on or included in other

¹⁴ For a foundational discussion of Linked Data principles, see Berners-Lee (2006). Methodologies developed prior to 2006, when the Linked Data principles were first introduced, do not incorporate these guidelines. For an overview of existing methodologies see Tudorache 2020; see also Poveda-Villalón et al. 2022, 2-3.

¹⁵ For a definition of semantic artefact, see Hugo et al. 2020, 12.

¹⁶ For instance, the ARIADNE Object Catalogue Ontology (<https://h-setis.cnr.it/ontologies/4>) lacks permanent identifiers and URI resolution, making it effectively inaccessible as a resource. Other established resources, such as Nomisma (<https://h-setis.cnr.it/ontologies/23>), are similarly absent from LOV.

catalogued resources, displaying relations and usage; external related projects are mapped as well. H-SeTIS adopts a pragmatic and flexible approach to classifying these resources, allowing the system to adapt to their evolving nature.

Additionally, H-SeTIS adheres to the FAIR principles and the Linked Open Data paradigm, providing API access and incorporating standard metadata schemas like Dublin Core and schema.org to enhance data interoperability, reusability, and discoverability. A curated bibliography is also part of the database, focusing on published materials related to semantic artefacts, alongside general references and resources useful for semantic web development, particularly in the Heritage field. This bibliography is managed through Zotero (<https://www.zotero.org/>) and integrates seamlessly with the database via Zotero's APIs, enabling smooth incorporation of bibliographic data into the user interface. The shared library is already available (<https://www.zotero.org/groups/5434475/>) and is currently being integrate in the H-SeTIS front-end using Kerko (<https://pypi.org/project/Kerko/>), a Python library for displaying Zotero's data through API. The bibliography does not only provide scientific references for the catalogued artefacts, but it is itself a source to find new artefacts that sometimes do not have a complete documentation accessible online because they never reached a sufficient implementation and are known only by publications or because they are inactive: H-SeTIS also records these cases to provide a general overview as much complete as possible.

Although the survey is still ongoing, the database currently includes drafts referred to 15 metadata standards, 94 ontologies, 137 thesauri, 4 application profiles and 4 software belonging to the Heritage domain.

Figure 4.1: Homepage of the H-SeTIS Database.

One of the primary objectives of the H-SeTIS database is to provide a comprehensive overview of the current state of ontologies and, more broadly, semantic artefacts within the Heritage field. This overview highlights specific sub-domains that have attracted community attention, such as archival science, numismatics, and heritage preservation. Additionally, it offers an updated dataset for identifying the classes and properties that domain experts and knowledge engineers regard as representative of Heritage, as well as the various perspectives from which the domain is viewed.

Additionally, the H-SeTIS survey highlights general trends and identifies significant challenges related to compliance with FAIR and Linked Open Data (LOD) principles. As thoroughly illustrated in the

database description (Scarpa and Valente 2024a), most semantic artefacts in the Heritage field do not fully meet these compliance standards.

Figure 4.2: Detail of the database record for the CIDOC CRM.

4.1 STATE OF THE ART AND NEW PERSPECTIVES

Summary Two predominant modeling approaches in Heritage ontologies and data models exist, *i.e.* event-based and object-based. The following paragraphs discuss the limitations of both methods, as explored by Dijkshoorn et al. (2018), while highlighting critical concepts relevant to their application. The CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CIDOC CRM), an object-oriented data model formalized

using ontology-compliant languages, contrasts with the Europeana Data Model (EDM), which serves as an application profile rather than a traditional ontology.

Among the semantic artefacts mapped in the H-SeTIS database and tailored for the Heritage domain, the two most common modeling approaches are event-based and object-based. While the limitations of both methods have been thoroughly examined by Dijkshoorn et al. (2018), several key concepts warrant further discussion. The authors weigh the pros and cons of these approaches evaluating the applications of CIDOC CRM and the Europeana Data Model (EDM)¹⁷.

Among the discussed challenges, specialization—which may also be referred to as *granularity*—is essential in developing a data model that balances generality and specificity to accurately describe the domain (Dijkshoorn et al. 2018, 260). The authors note that the CIDOC CRM defines 82 top-level classes, whereas the EDM describes 18. However, in both frameworks, all Tangible Entities are classified as instances of either `cidoc:E71_Human-Made_Thing` or `edm:ProvidedCHO`, defined as «discrete, identifiable human-made items that are documented as single units»¹⁸ and «Cultural Heritage objects that Europeana collects descriptions about»¹⁹ respectively. There is no inherently correct choice between these approaches, as each model is designed to address specific needs. The optimal solution is one that maintains a balance between overly complex models and those that are excessively generic.

Dijkshoorn et al. (2018) also discuss ontological commitment, which refers to the way concepts are defined and structured within a domain based on a chosen interpretation (e.g., the concept of “Actor” in the CIDOC CRM vs `schema.org`)²⁰. The level of commitment directly affects how well the model can be applied across different contexts, influencing its flexibility and applicability (Salustri 2000). The CIDOC CRM demonstrates a higher ontological commitment than the EDM, as most of its concepts are modeled according to the CIDOC CRM’s specific interpretation (see also further). A higher ontological commitment typically leads to greater precision, but this often comes at the expense of reusability. In contrast, the EDM’s lower ontological commitment promotes flexibility, although it may introduce alignment challenges when integrating with other models. Generally, models with lower ontological commitment offer higher reusability, as they are less complex and more adaptable to various applications (Studer, Benjamins, and Fensel 1998, 187).

Another significant challenge lies in the coexistence of object- and event-centric approaches: the choice between these approaches depends on the nature of the information being conveyed and the objectives of the data model. Object-centric models are focused on the Tangible Entity, an approach that aligns with traditional cataloging systems used in libraries and museum collections. Conversely, the event-centric model, describes Tangible Entities through the events they are involved with. This method documents in greater detail activities such as production, acquisition, and movement, while linking artefacts to relevant entities such as the creators, owners, locations, and dates tied to the TE. While the object-centric approach may struggle to effectively capture temporal changes, the event-centric approach can generate intricate and lengthy data paths, reflecting its inherent complexity.

Dijkshoorn et al. (2018) also propose six essential requirements to guide institutions in making informed decisions when selecting or developing data models. Among these requirements is the notion that «generic and specific modeling approaches can be combined by creating ontologies that can be specialized» (requirement 1). The ontology presented here reflects this principle, designed with flexibility to allow future extensions in specific subdomains. Furthermore, CH data models should

¹⁷ <https://h-setis.cnr.it/ontologies/5>. It is important to emphasize that, as illustrated below, the CIDOC CRM is an object-oriented data model that has subsequently been formalized using ontology-compliant languages such as RDFS and OWL. In contrast, the EDM is technically an application profile rather than an ontology. The observations made by Dijkshoorn et al. (2018) should be understood as addressing a broader spectrum of semantic artefacts, of which an ontology is only one specific type.

¹⁸ CIDOC CRM v.7.1.3, 97-99.

¹⁹ Europeana Foundation 2017, 15.

²⁰ The class `cidoc:E21_Person` is defined as «real persons who live or are assumed to have lived», while `schema:Person` is defined as «A person (alive, dead, undead, or fictional)». Notwithstanding the similarity, the CIDOC CRM provides no alignment to `schema.org`.

support the recording of both attributes (descriptive properties of Tangible Entities) and events (changes over time); a model that is too object-centric may lack the ability to describe temporal data effectively (requirement 2), and should support the documentation of changes over time (requirement 3).

Moreover, it is crucial to distinguish between the TE itself and its representations (3D models, digital twins, [H-]BIM; requirement 4). Data models should also accommodate multiple sources that may provide differing or even conflicting descriptions of the same TE. As data is increasingly published online, the presence of multiple, potentially inconsistent descriptions becomes inevitable. Allowing for conflicting views is essential to ensuring that users can access all available perspectives and make informed decisions about which data to trust (requirement 5).

4.2 MAIN CLASSES OF EXISTING HS/CH ONTOLOGIES: THE ARCO AND BEARCHAEO EXAMPLES

Summary Two ontologies are relevant for discussion on the modeling strategies discussed in the previous section: the Architecture of Knowledge Ontology (ArCo Network) and the Beyond Archaeology (BeArchaeo) ontology. The ArCo Ontology introduces a situation-centric modeling approach, expanding on the traditional event-based framework of the CIDOC CRM. Conversely, the BeArchaeo ontology is tailored to model excavation data with a focus on the relationship between archaeological findings and their archaeometric analyses.

In addition to the conclusions drawn by Dijkshoorn et al. (2018), it is worthwhile to provide a brief overview of two ontologies that are highly relevant for the Heritage Science (HS) field. The first is the Architecture of Knowledge Ontology, which further refines the event-based approach by proposing a situation-based perspective. The second is the Beyond Archaeology (BeArchaeo) ontology, which models archaeological findings and their relationships with archaeometric analyses.

The Architecture of Knowledge Ontology (ArCo Network)²¹ is defined by its creators as a situation-centric model (Carriero et al. 2021, 326): contrary to the CIDOC CRM, which is an event-based model, ArCo models not just events but the entire relational context involving objects, people, places, and times, *i.e.* a situation. It reuses several core classes from ontologies within the OntoPiA network, the Italian Public Administration's ontology ecosystem²². Key ArCo classes include `l0:Entity`²³, which subsumes `cis:CulturalEntity`²⁴ and its subclass `arco:CulturalProperty`²⁵, as well as `arco:EventOrSituation`²⁶. Cultural Property includes several subclasses: `arco:ComplexCulturalProperty`²⁷, which is defined by its various components, and `arco:TangibleCulturalProperty`/`arco:IntangibleCulturalProperty`²⁸. Tangible Cultural Property is further divided into `arco:ArchaeologicalCulturalProperty`, `arco:MovableCulturalProperty`²⁹, and `arco:ImmovableCulturalProperty`.

²¹ <https://h-setis.cnr.it/ontologies/42>

²² <https://github.com/italia/daf-ontologie-vocabolari-controllati>.

²³ Imported from L0, <https://w3id.org/italia/onto/I0/Entity>, described as «anything: real possible, or imaginary, which some modeler wants to talk about for some purpose.» L0 (Level-0) is a top-level ontology for OntoPiA.

²⁴ Imported from Cultural Ontology, <http://dati.beniculturali.it/cis/CulturalEntity>, described as a «class that provides a generalization for the three classes of cultural institution and place, collection and cultural object».

²⁵ Described as representing «a cultural property, both tangible and intangible. A cultural property is the legacy, tangible or intangible, recognised as part of the national cultural heritage, since it helps know and reconstruct the history and the landscape». This class is the union of subclasses Tangible Cultural Property and Intangible Cultural Property.

²⁶ <https://w3id.org/italia/onto/I0/EventOrSituation>. «Any entity that typically flows in time, either in the physical or social world. Examples include atmospheric phenomena, concerts, travels, institutional processes, etc. It also represents a relational context created by an observer on the basis of a frame. Events are opposable to objects, since events typically flow in time, aggregating multiple objects during their flow, while objects tend to be stable in a certain time interval. This class represents a specific situation or an event that happens in the lifecycle of either a business or a person or a group of persons».

²⁷ Defined as «a complex cultural property, that consists of different components».

²⁸ A cultural property «part of cultural heritage represented by ephemeral performances of traditional manifestations, techniques, knowledge»; «a tangible cultural property, either immovable or movable».

²⁹ Defined as «a movable cultural property, that is, an object or an artefact that can be moved in various ways».

The Beyond Archaeology (BeArchaeo) ontology is designed to model excavation data with an emphasis on the relationship between archaeological findings and the archaeometric analyses performed on them (Lombardo et al. 2020, 2023)³⁰. It specifically focuses on representing archaeological knowledge as typically recorded by excavators in field and lab reports (Lombardo et al. 2020, 703–4). For example, two of its main classes, Archaeological Finding and Stratigraphic Unit, are modeled after the records used by the ICCD. The BeArchaeo ontology is designed primarily to describe archaeological objects themselves rather than the processes by which they were formed. In other words, its main focus is on detailing the characteristics and attributes of the objects discovered during excavations. In terms of temporal representation, the BeArchaeo ontology addresses time solely from a historical perspective through the class `bearchaeo:Chronology`³¹.

4.3 THE CIDOC CONCEPTUAL REFERENCE MODEL

Summary The CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CIDOC CRM) serves as a structured framework for describing and organizing information about CH. Initially developed in 1996 by the Documentation Standards Group of the Comité International pour la Documentation (CIDOC) of the International Council of Museums (ICOM), the CIDOC CRM aims to enhance semantic interoperability across various types of museum data and their relationships with archival and library materials. Despite its foundations in RDF and RDFS, the CIDOC CRM's expressiveness is limited due to RDFS's constraints in handling advanced features such as property quantification and complex class expressions. The lack of semantic enforcement for cardinality and other restrictions poses significant challenges for data modeling and interoperability, leading to potential inconsistencies in data representation across different systems.

The CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (hereafter, CIDOC CRM) is a framework designed to help describe and organize information about CH, like artefacts and events³². It was first developed in 1996 by the Documentation Standards Group of the Comité International pour la Documentation (CIDOC) of the International Council of Museums (ICOM). This initiative aimed to create a domain ontology, structured as an object-oriented semantic model³³, to resolve the challenges of semantic interoperability across various types of museum data and their connections to archival and library materials. In September 2000, the CIDOC CRM was officially accepted as a work item by the ISO Technical Interoperability committee (ISO TC46/SC4) and became an ISO standard in 2006³⁴. The CIDOC CRM was not designed for seamless integration into the Semantic Web ecosystem or to fully leverage the capabilities offered by standards such as RDFS and OWL, as it lacks a formal specification for its semantic and inferential apparatus, resulting in the absence of a well-defined framework to support fundamental operations such as querying, consistency checking, and reasoning within a CIDOC CRM-based knowledge base (Meghini and Doerr 2018).

To be more specific, the CIDOC CRM has utilized the RDF (Gandon and Schreiber 2014) data model and its RDFS (Brickley and Guha 2014) extension for representing concepts, relationships, and

³⁰ For such purpose the developers adopted the field records of the ICCD described at <https://iccd.beniculturali.it/it/ricercanormative/170/us-usm-schede-%20per-il-rilevamento-sul-campo-delle-unit-stratigrafiche> (last visit 2-10-2024).

³¹ <http://purl.org/bearchaeo/Archeo-ontology#Chronology>, «the chronology of the stratigraphic unit or archaeological finding».

³² <https://h-setis.cnr.it/ontologies/view/3>. The version of the CIDOC CRM referenced throughout this document is the latest official ISO release, v.7.1.3. The formal definition can be found at https://cidoc-crm.org/sites/default/files/cidoc_crm_version_7.1.3.pdf; references to its specific sections will include page numbers in the format: CIDOC CRM v.7.1.3, 10.

³³ An object-oriented semantic model combines object-oriented design (OOD), which structures data as objects with attributes and relationships, and semantic modeling, which focuses on defining the meaning and context of those objects and their relationships. In OOD, objects represent real-world entities. In contrast, description logic (DL) models, which are widely used in ontological modeling, emphasize defining logical relationships between entities through formal rules and constraints rather than relying on the object-centric encapsulation of data. DL models focus on the formal definition of classes and properties using axioms and rules, enabling complex reasoning about the data, including inference and automated reasoning.

³⁴ <https://cidoc.mini.icom.museum/working-groups/crm-special-interest-group/> (last visit 2-10-2024). The third edition of the ISO standard was released in 2023 (ISO Standard 2023).

hierarchies since version 7.1.1³⁵. While RDF provides a foundational structure for data representation using triples (subject-predicate-object), RDFS builds upon RDF by allowing basic ontology modeling. However, RDFS is limited in expressiveness as it does not support advanced features such as property quantification³⁶ or complex class expressions. These capabilities are provided by the Web Ontology Language (OWL) (M. K. Smith, Welty, and McGuinness 2004), which enhances the representation of knowledge in more sophisticated ways. Consequently, the CIDOC CRM's reliance on RDF and RDFS limits its expressiveness and complicates the execution of advanced tasks such as ensuring logical consistency within the data or processing complex queries.

Meghini and Doerr (2018) further argue that RDFS and OWL, while practical for system implementation, are not ideally suited as abstract formal models. In particular, the use of International Resource Identifiers (IRIs), which are essential in RDF and OWL to uniquely identify resources, is considered unnecessarily complex and ill-suited for expressing the formal structure of CIDOC CRM as they are over-complicated for human understanding and unnecessary when trying to describe or model concepts. Consequently, the CIDOC CRM has also been formalized using first-order logic, a system widely used in fields such as mathematics and computer science to describe relationships and properties with simplicity and clarity. For instance, `cidoc:E5_Event` is defined in first-order logic as $E5(x) \Rightarrow E4(x)$, meaning 'if x is an instance of `cidoc:E5_Event`, then x is also an instance of `cidoc:E4_Period`'. This expression captures the subclass relationship where every E5 Event is also a type of E4 Period.

Notwithstanding these characteristics of the CRM, a preliminary RDFS implementation of the latest official version of CIDOC CRM (version 7.1.3) has been released³⁷ and an OWL implementation has been developed by researchers at Erlangen University. The OWL (OWL-DL 1.0) implementation, known as CIDOC Erlangen³⁸, formalizes existential and cardinality restrictions. For example, the class `cidoc:E67_Birth` is defined as a subclass with an existential restriction, which specifies that the property `cidoc:P98_brought_into_life` must always have a value belonging to the class `cidoc:E21_Person`. This means that in a specific instance of `cidoc:E67_Birth`, such as "the birth of Xerxes," the property `cidoc:P98_brought_into_life` would reference an individual entity that is classified as `cidoc:E21_Person`, ensuring that Xerxes is recognized as a person brought into life by that event.

In the original CIDOC CRM, cardinality restrictions are provided for clarification purposes but are not formalized within the model. This means that while they are documented in the official definition, they are not semantically enforced. Semantic enforcement is like setting rules that everyone has to follow to make sure the data adheres to defined specifications. With semantic enforcement, the system checks these relationships automatically. So, if someone tries to say that a person had two different birth events, the system would flag it as an error. For instance, the cardinality (referred to as *quantification*³⁹ in CIDOC documentation) of `cidoc:P98_brought_into_life` is described as "one to many, dependent (0,n:1,1)"⁴⁰. This signifies that on the domain side (*i.e.*, `cidoc:E67_Birth`), a single birth event can bring multiple people into existence (e.g., twins), while on the range side (*i.e.*, `cidoc:E21_Person`), each person is associated with exactly one birth event, as no individual can be born more than once.

³⁵ On the RDFS implementation, see below. Up to version 7.0 the CIDOC CRM was formalized as an XML schema. See the list of versions available at <https://cidoc-crm.org/versions-of-the-cidoc-crm> (last visit 2-10-2024).

³⁶ The ability to express statements about the number of relationships (properties) that can exist between classes or individuals, e.g. "every person has exactly one biological mother."

³⁷ Git versioning of the RDFS implementation of CIDOC since version 7.1.1 is underway and tracked here: https://gitlab.isl.ics.forth.gr/cidoc-crm/cidoc_crm_rdf (last visit: 30-09-2024).

³⁸ <https://h-setis.cnr.it/ontologies/view/127>.

³⁹ Twelve of such property quantifiers are defined in CIDOC CRM v.7.1.3, 21-22. On quantifiers, see also Sanfilippo, Markhoff, and Pittet 2020, 108.

⁴⁰ CIDOC CRM v.7.1.3, 164

The lack of semantic enforcement for cardinality and other restrictions in the original CIDOC CRM has significant implications for data modeling and interoperability. Without formalized constraints, there is a risk of inconsistent interpretations among different systems and implementations, leading to potential inaccuracies in data representation. For instance, while the documentation states that the property `cidoc:P98_brought_into_life` has a cardinality of “one to many,” this does not prevent users from misapplying the property in ways that violate these guidelines. Consequently, data consumers may encounter challenges when integrating datasets from diverse sources, as varying interpretations can result in conflicts and ambiguity in relationships. For example, the property `cidoc:P11_had_participant`, which connects the class `cidoc:E5_Event` with `cidoc:E39_Actor`, is defined with a cardinality of “many to many (0,n:0,n)”⁴¹. This allows events to exist without any participants and permits actors to engage in zero or multiple events. However, this flexibility can result in divergent formalizations: while some users may adhere to the original cardinality, others might impose restrictions on E39 Actor, requiring at least one actor for each event. While models based on the latter interpretation can encompass those of the former, the reverse is not true, leading to potential mismatches in data representation. As a consequence, this variability can impede applications’ ability to interoperate effectively, as different systems may interpret the same cardinality in different ways. Without clearer guidelines and standards for interpreting cardinalities, the risk of fragmented and poorly interoperable data models increases, complicating data exchange and integration efforts across various platforms.

From a practical perspective, the absence of enforced cardinality restrictions and mandatory domain/range properties in the CIDOC CRM results in a more flexible model, albeit with the aforementioned challenges related to interoperability and system integration. On the other hand, strict enforcement of domain and range constraints, as implemented in the CIDOC Erlangen version, can lead to unintended consequences. For example, it may overly constrain data models, limiting flexibility in cases where exceptions are necessary, or result in undesired or even unwanted inferences.

4.4 LEVERAGING NEW TECHNOLOGIES

Summary The preceding sections classified models representing the Heritage domain into two primary categories: event-based and object-based, noting their non-mutually exclusive nature. It further addressed significant limitations associated with the CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CIDOC CRM). A critical issue for knowledge graphs based on the CIDOC CRM is the integration of legacy or preexisting data. The DIGILAB, as a brand new platform, provides a unique opportunity to propose a novel model for representing the Heritage Science domain. This new model emphasizes the ‘object’ (*i.e.*, TE) and its role in research.

The previous paragraphs outlined how models developed to represent the Heritage domain can be classified into two main categories: event-based and object-based, and that these categories are not mutually exclusive. Additionally, the discussion highlighted some of the significant drawbacks associated with the primary model and ISO standard adopted in the Heritage field, namely the CIDOC CRM. While the CIDOC CRM is a comprehensive and complex model, it has limitations, such as the inability to support complex reasoning and challenges related to interoperability and system integration. Nevertheless, it is the product of two decades of work in KE and OE focused on the Heritage domain.

One of the major challenges that CIDOC CRM-based knowledge graphs face is the integration of preexisting data. The collaborations with Ontotext (<https://www.ontotext.com/>; Alexiev 2012; Alexiev et al. 2013) have shown that the CIDOC CRM working group needed to address a vast pool of preexisting data while designing relevant user queries. By employing a Fundamental Relations approach, Ontotext was able to simplify CIDOC CRM’s potentially complex queries, resulting in

⁴¹ Sanfilippo, Markhoff, and Pittet 2020, 108-109. CIDOC CRM v.7.1.3, 121-122.

enhanced semantic querying of a knowledge graph comprising 2,051,797 museum objects, 415,509 thesaurus entries, 195,208,156 explicit statements, and a 42 GB repository⁴². Since the DIGILAB is a new platform with no preexisting knowledge graph, it offers the unique opportunity to propose a new model for the representation of the Heritage Science domain, focused on the ‘object’ (*i.e.*, a TE) and a special consideration of its role in the field of research, rather than as «the things preserved by the memory institutions, *i.e.*, museums, sites and monuments records [...], archives and libraries» (Doerr 2009, 464), which is the definition of TE embraced by the CIDOC CRM.

As for complex reasoning, in RDFS, `rdfs:domain` and `rdfs:range` are essential for defining relationships between properties and the classes of resources they can be applied to, but over-reliance on these can sometimes complicate the use of broader or more nuanced data structures⁴³. The `rdfs:domain` property specifies which class the subject of a triple is necessarily a member of, establishing a context for the property’s use. On the other hand, `rdfs:range` specifies which class the object of a triple is necessarily a member of.⁴⁴ In the case of a property such as `cidoc:P108_has_produced`⁴⁵ the subject of a triple must be an instance `cidoc:E12_Production` (domain) and the object an instance of `cidoc:E24_Physical_Human-Made_Thing` (range). The triple `ex:CreationOfTheMonaLisa P108_has_produced ex:MonaLisa` is valid because subject and object belong to the correct classes. But if the same property is used for a triple such as `ex:BattleOfWaterloo P108_has_produced ex:StrategyDocument` the model would incorrectly infer that the Battle of Waterloo is an instance of `cidoc:E12_Production`, which is a category for production activities designed to create new items (like making a physical object or artefact)⁴⁶.

Tibaut and Guerra De Oliveira (2022) measured the appropriateness of the CIDOC CRM for reuse in an ontology for the Built Heritage domain. Their in-depth evaluation of the CIDOC CRM’s metrics and value scores with reference to specific parameters, provides valuable insight into the CIDOC CRM’s structure. Their approach involved developing a new ontology evaluation framework, building upon the OQuaRE (*Ontology Quality Requirements and Evaluation*) framework (Wilson et al. 2022). Using Java software based on the Apache Jena Ontology API, the researchers identified and corrected errors in OQuaRE’s original metrics. They applied the improved framework to evaluate the CIDOC CRM across several parameters, including the number of external ontologies used, composability (*i.e.*, how well it incorporates external ontologies through a name-spacing mechanism), and aggregability (the contribution of external ontologies within the CIDOC CRM).

The CIDOC CRM obtained the lowest scores for the Reliability and Functional Adequacy parameters. Reliability measures how well the ontology keeps working over time without issues. It is based on several factors, including how deep the structure is (from general to specific concepts). The CIDOC CRM’s score for this parameter is low because it has a very detailed, 10-level structure that includes both broad and very specific concepts, which makes it harder to maintain consistently⁴⁷. This detailed

⁴² This integration was carried out in the development of the Researchspace platform (<https://researchspace.org/>) and the data pool was that of the British Museum database; Alexiev et al. 2013.

⁴³ On `rdfs:domain` and `rdfs:range` see Uschold 2022, 84-85. See also the RDFS W3C Recommendation (Brickley and Guha 2014).

⁴⁴ If the property `ex:writtenBy` has the domain `ex:book` and the range `ex:author`, the subject of given triple must be a book, and the object must be an author. Therefore, the triple `ex:NaturalHistory ex:writtenBy ex:PlinyTheElder` is valid because the *Natural History* is correctly classified as an instance of the class `ex:book`, and Pliny the Elder is correctly classified as an instance of the class `ex:author`. However, the `rdfs:domain` and `rdfs:range` assert not just that “books are written by authors,” but rather that “anything written by an author is a book”. For instance, in the fictional triple `ex:Rome ex:writtenBy ex:PlinyTheElder`, `ex:Rome` would be incorrectly inferred as a `ex:book` due to the domain constraint.

⁴⁵ CIDOC CRM v.7.1.3, 171: «this property identifies the instance of E24 Physical Human-Made Thing that came into existence as a result of the instance of E12 Production».

⁴⁶ Note that according to the CIDOC CRM, the Battle of Waterloo is an instance of `cidoc:E7_Event`.

⁴⁷ This is the case of concepts such as `cidoc:E34_Inscription`, a class defined as comprising “recognisable texts that can be attached to instances of E24 Physical Human-Made Thing”, which is a subclass of (in order): `< cidoc:E37_Mark < cidoc:E36_VisualItem < cidoc:E73_InformationObject < cidoc:E90_SymbolicObject < cidoc:E28_ConceptualObject < cidoc:E71_HumanMadeThing < cidoc:E70_Thing < cidoc:E77_PersistentItem < cidoc:E1_CRM_Entity`. See also Alexiev et al. (2013), 7. This is CIDOC’s deepest branch; note however, that multiple inheritance is also present, as `cidoc:E34_LinguisticObject` is a superclass of `cidoc:E34_Inscription`.

structure affects its overall reliability score. Furthermore, the evaluation of the CIDOC CRM's Functional Adequacy measures how well it supports applications by providing useful relationships and properties. Its score is low because of weak performance in key metrics measuring Relationship Richness, Attribute Richness, and Class Richness. Relationship Richness specifically looks at the balance between the number of subclass relationships (`rdfs:subClassOf`) and the total number of object and data properties (`owl:ObjectProperty`, `owl:DatatypeProperty`). In the CIDOC CRM, there are 163 subclass relationships and 309 object and data properties (v.7.1.3). For example, the concept `cidoc:E18_Physical_Thing` contributes three subclass relationships (`cidoc:E19_Physical_Object` and `cidoc:E24_Physical_Human-Made_Thing`, `cidoc:E26_Physical_Feature`) and thirteen object properties. This imbalance, with more object and data properties than subclass relationships, results in the low Functional Adequacy score.

It must also be stressed that, at present, the CIDOC CRM does not natively reuse identical concepts from other ontologies. It defines its own unique classes and properties specifically crafted to meet the needs of CH data modeling, *i.e.*, it has a high ontological commitment, as described in [State of the Art and New Perspectives](#). Unlike other ontologies that may reuse concepts from shared vocabularies (such as FOAF or Schema.org) by importing them or directly linking to their URIs, CIDOC CRM originally established a distinct conceptual model. This means that even when its concepts are semantically similar to those found in other ontologies, the CIDOC CRM defines its own versions rather than reusing or aligning with existing concepts from external sources by default.⁴⁸

5 DEVELOPING AN ONTOLOGY FOR HERITAGE SCIENCE

5.1 METHODOLOGY FOR THE NEW HERITAGE SCIENCE ONTOLOGY

Summary Ontology development is a structured process involving several key phases to ensure that the resulting ontology is robust, useful, and effectively serves its intended purpose. The typical development methodology encompasses activities such as requirements specification, design, implementation, evaluation, publication, and maintenance. The Linked Open Terms (LOT) methodology is a lightweight approach designed primarily for industry projects but offers valuable tools for ontology development in Heritage studies. It emphasizes the reuse of terms from existing ontologies and vocabularies. The LOT methodology includes four core activities: requirements specification, implementation, publication, and maintenance. Overall, a structured approach to ontology development, particularly within the Heritage domain, can enhance the efficacy and applicability of ontologies, fostering better integration and reuse across various projects and systems.

Ontology development is a structured process involving several key phases to ensure that the resulting ontology is robust, useful, and effectively serves its intended purpose. The development methodology typically includes activities such as requirements specification, design, implementation, evaluation, publication, and maintenance. Tudorache (2020) offers a review of the most popular OE methods: none of these is specifically tailored for the Heritage field.

The Linked Open Terms (LOT) methodology (Poveda-Villalón et al. 2022) is described as «a lightweight methodology for developing ontologies and vocabularies focused on industry projects». Although primarily designed for the industrial sector, it also provides useful lightweight tools for ontology development in Heritage studies. The methodology emphasizes the reuse of terms from existing ontologies and vocabularies⁴⁹, and the publication of the final product in accordance with Linked Data

⁴⁸ The definition of `cidoc:E5_Event` is somehow similar to `schema:Event` (<https://schema.org/Event>) which is defined as “[a]n event happening at a certain time and location, such as a concert, lecture, or festival.”

⁴⁹ For a discussion on ontology reuse, see Poveda Villalón, Suárez-Figueroa, and Gómez-Pérez (2012) and the summary in Poveda-Villalón et al. 2022, 9–10. The authors divide ontology reuse into *hard* and *soft*: hard reuse involves the direct import of an entire ontology, while soft reuse refers to referencing specific element URIs without importing the full ontology. Poveda-Villalón et al. (2022, 10) also recommend conducting ontology reuse in tandem with the ontology encoding process. Once the model has stabilized, developers should search for

principles. Drawing from other methodologies, the LOT includes four activities: requirements specification, implementation, publication, and maintenance (Fig.5.1).

Figure 5.1: Main phases of the LOT methodology

The first step is the **ontology requirements specification** activity, which involves collecting and defining the necessary requirements that the ontology must meet. These requirements are usually linked to the ontology's objectives, the specific domain it will represent, and technical aspects such as the implementation language, along with its target audience, intended uses, and the set of requirements it must fulfill. This involves collaboration with domain experts to understand their specific needs and the context in which the ontology will be used. In order to define how the ontology will be used, specific scenarios or use-cases where the ontology is applied should be outlined: this helps determine the necessary classes, properties, and relationships. Functional and non-functional requirements are documented to ensure that all relevant aspects are considered before moving forward. A glossary of the terms of the ontology is also under development (Suárez-Figueroa, Gómez-Pérez, and Fernández-López 2015, 111–12).

Once the requirements are established, the **design phase** focuses on creating the structural framework of the ontology (ontology implementation). This phase typically includes defining the key concepts and relationships in the domain, formally implementing the using appropriate tools and languages, such as OWL (Web Ontology Language), as well as preliminary testing.

Finally, the publication phase aims to make the ontology accessible for both human and machine use, ensuring it can be reused and integrated within other systems. After publication, **ontology maintenance** is crucial for ensuring the ontology remains relevant and accurate throughout its life cycle. This activity addresses situations that may arise post-publication, including bug detection and new requirements identification.

existing ontologies that align with its structure. During the encoding phase, developers should identify and incorporate relevant ontologies, which often requires a survey of existing models. As a result, the original conceptualization may be revised based on the findings from the reuse process.

5.1.1 Development of Functional Requirements

Summary A significant focus has been placed on defining functional requirements and use cases, with the goal of guiding the ontology's development effectively. A common technique employed in this process is the creation of Competency Questions (CQs), which serve as informal requirements outlining what the ontology needs to achieve. These questions are well-established methods for clarifying the intended functionality of the ontology. To complement these CQs, a top-down approach was taken by interviewing several domain experts to gather insights into the types of results they would like from a resource designed to manage Heritage Science data. The suggested queries varied widely in scope and detail, presenting a critical challenge for ontology modeling.

At present, the ontology requirements specification and implementation are being carried out. In particular, functional requirements and use-cases have been created. The definition of functional ontology requirements aims to produce a set of requirements that guide the development of the ontology: one common technique used for this purpose is the creation of Competency Questions (CQs). These are a well-established method for defining what the ontology needs to achieve (Grüniger and Fox 1995): this approach involves creating a set of queries that the ontology should be able to answer once it is fully developed and act as informal requirements, laying out the scope of the ontology's functionality.

These CQs should focus on assessing the various roles and expertise within the domain and identifying the specific queries that the ontology should be able to address. Several domain experts were interviewed to gather insights into the types of results they would like to obtain from a resource capable of managing Heritage Science data. The suggested queries varied widely in scope and detail, presenting a key challenge for ontology modeling: developing a model that is both general enough to accommodate diverse needs and specific enough to be practically useful. Some example queries proposed during these interviews include:

- What materials is a given TE it composed of?
- What is the conservation status of a specific work? Are there any degradation products? If so, what are they and where are they located?
- Are there other versions of a certain TE? If so, where are they? Have they been studied? How are they similar or different from the work I am studying?
- Is it possible to determine in which archaeological sites a given association of artefacts or materials is present?
- Are all the materials in a specific work original, or are there any restorations/retouches? If so, what were they made of and where are they located?
- For tangible entities that bear marks left by other tangible entities (e.g., seals, tools), is it possible to identify the former based on the chronology of the latter?
- When was the restoration of a certain work carried out? Is there any information about who performed it and what materials were used?
- In what environment was an artefact stored? How did this environment affect the artefact's state of preservation? (e.g., buried for centuries; exposed to light; exposed to rain; exposed to chlorine sources; exposed to high temperatures...)
- If the object of study is a painted or decorated artefact: what pigments are present? How are they distributed? How were they applied (*i.e.*, were they mixed? Are there overlapping layers)? Was there a preparation layer for the colors? What is the support made of (e.g., the type of wood for a painted panel; the composition of the ceramic for a decorated vase)?
- I found an unusual pigment during a diagnostic campaign. Are there other works where this pigment has been found? Is it compatible with the time period of the work being analyzed?
- I have collected a spectrum that I cannot interpret. Are there any spectra similar to mine? If so, how was it interpreted?

5.1.2 Use Cases & Scenarios

Summary A use case outlines specific scenarios where a user interacts with a system to achieve a goal, capturing the steps, actions, and system responses involved. This structured approach aids in defining system requirements by answering core questions about who uses the system, their objectives, and the system's response. In the following sections, nine use cases are sketched.

In modern systems design and development, understanding how users interact with a system or product is crucial for success. One of the most effective tools to capture and communicate these interactions is the use case. Originating from software engineering and now widely used across various industries, a use case describes a specific scenario in which a user interacts with a product to achieve a desired outcome (Jacobson, Spence, and Kerr 2016). By providing a structured, narrative approach to these interactions, use cases offer an effective means of understanding and modelling system requirements.

A use case is essentially a description of how a system, product, or service behaves in response to specific actions initiated by an external actor (Kendall and McGuinness 2019, 25–44; Cockburn 2000, 1–3). The actor can be a human user or another system that interacts with the product to accomplish a specific goal. A well-written use case outlines the interactions between the actor and the system, detailing the sequence of steps taken to achieve the desired outcome.

At its core, a use case answers the following questions:

- Who is using the system?
- What are they trying to achieve?
- How does the system respond to the user's actions?

For example, in a CH database application, a use case might describe the steps a museum curator takes to input TE data into a digital archive, query the database for specific types of TEs, or generate reports on a set of TEs. The narrative would include who the user is (a curator, a Heritage researcher, etc.), the actions they perform (data entry, querying for information such as TE age, origin, or material), and the outcome (data gathering, academic research, etc.).

Use cases usually follow a structure that includes a title or description, the actors involved, preconditions (what must be true for the use case to begin), the main success scenario (the steps leading to a successful outcome), alternate flows (what happens when variations occur), and postconditions (the expected state of the system after the interaction is complete). The versatility of use cases makes them a valuable tool in various industries and fields. While they are most commonly associated with software development, their applications extend far beyond technology, offering a structured approach to understanding interactions in complex systems. In addition, use-cases are iterative, meaning that they can be improved as the development proceeds, and should be tailored to the development needs (Cockburn 2000, 7–9).

Although the practice of building use cases in the Humanities is not widely widespread as in other fields, their use is a relevant aid in the development of digital tools, although only a few cases are documented in academic publications (York, Wulfman, and Crane 2003; Teehan and Keating 2010). The methodology here applied for the development of use cases is that suggested and outlined in Poveda-Villalón et al. (2022, 4–5). The scope of the use cases was focused on the wider realm of HS, especially considering the disciplines of Archaeology, Epigraphy and Conservation Sciences. Nine distinct use cases were created in order to conceive distinct possible scenarios as potentially envisioned by HS experts. These will be improved and refined also considering other approached to use case modeling (Jacobson 1992; Cockburn 2000).

Use Case 1 – Rock inscription

Description: Several inscriptions are found on a natural rock that is hardly accessible. Some are engraved, some are painted; they probably belong to different periods. The inscription must be

analyzed to identify the tools used to create them, as well as the pigments used. They must be recorded, interpreted and published, possibly relating them to other known cases. The rock that bears the inscriptions must be geolocalized and possibly included within a protected area.

Actors: researchers, instruments

Flow: the position of the rock is measured with a GPS system. The inscriptions are surveyed by an epigraphist that makes a preliminary identification of the various texts. Pictures of the entire rock and of single details of the inscriptions are taken; the size of the inscriptions is recorded as well. Using portable instruments, a profile of the marks is reconstructed; at the same time the spectrum of the pigments is analyzed. Both measurements are carried out through non-contact methods. Data collected on the field are processed in the office and laboratory. Geodata are managed in a GIS while other data is collected in databases.

Figure 5.2: Rock graffito by Juan de Oñate, El Morro National Monument, New Mexico (George A. Grant, Public domain, via Wikimedia Commons)

Use Case 2 – Medieval codex

Description: a medieval codex stored in an historical library reveals a new text that was previously unknown being erased in the past (palimpsest). The new text must be interpreted and photographed. The pigment of the ink must be analyzed along with the technique used to erase it. The genetic profile of the parchment must be determined in order to give clues of its provenance. The presence of possible biological decay must be also assessed.

Actors: researchers, instruments

Flow: the codex is moved from the library into a research facility. Non-invasive analyses of the ink pigments are carried out. A small sample of the parchment is taken to identify its genetic profile through laboratory amplification and analysis. Sample of the surface film is taken without any material loss in order to assess the presence of fungi or moulds. The pages are observed with an optical microscope to verify if the previous text was erased using a mechanical action. The pages are lighted up with UV light in order to reveal the previous text and take readable pictures, so that the text is correctly transcribed and interpreted, and later published. As the revealed text is a musical text, the music is therefore performed with real music instruments.

Figure 5.3: Mantova, Biblioteca Comunale Teresiana, MS 287, f. 1v (Biblioteca Digitale Teresiana)

Use Case 3 – Cuneiform tablet

Description: a cuneiform tablet from a private collection is published. Its original archaeological context is lost. The published tablet together with the remaining texts belonging to the private collection is returned to the Iraq Museum

Actors: researchers, museum curators

Flow: The tablet is cleaned, and a picture is taken using the ammonium chloride technique. Chemical composition information of the clay is obtained via X-ray fluorescence before the tablet is permanently returned to the Iraq Museum. The content is transliterated, translated, and subsequently published.

Figure 5.4: CBS 13972+ cuneiform tablet (Penn Museum)

Use Case 4 – Royal Inscription

Description: three different objects, originating from pioneering archaeological investigations or illegal trade, bear the same inscription. The objects are now kept in three different museums across Europe and the USA. No specific analyses have been performed on the objects. Different scholars offer

multiple editions of the text appearing on three objects in different moments. One was excavated in 1895/1900, but archaeological data is unavailable; one originates from the antiquities market and was acquired by a museum in the 1910s, its provenience and authenticity are debated; one was acquired by a museum from a private collector in the 1970s.

Actors: researchers, museum curators

Flow: The researcher aims to locate various objects bearing the same royal Akkadian inscription, gathering information on their locations and publication status. A review of the bibliography and critical editions leads to the identification of three objects bearing this specific inscription, with each one housed in a different museum. After visiting each location, the researcher determines that none of the objects are currently on display; furthermore, one of them has sustained critical damage. Chemical analyses are conducted to ascertain the original materials. Restoration work is performed as needed. Detailed photographs are taken, and the inscription is transliterated, translated, and subsequently published.

Figure 5.5: Metal bowl (IMJ 74.49.99, © CDLI); vase (?) in the shape of a shell (MRAH O.710, © CDLI); perforated pedestal (AO 3296, Musée du Louvre)

Use Case 5 – Neo-Assyrian Cylinder seal

Description: A cylinder seal is part of a museum collection. No information on its acquisition is available. The seal bears a scene with standing figures. An inscription bearing the name of the (presumed) original owner is present.

Actors: researchers

Flow: The object is meticulously examined and measured using optical microscopes to determine its production techniques. Petrographic analyses are conducted to identify the specific type of stone utilized. Image acquisition techniques are employed to generate a 3D replica of the object. The iconography and inscription are closely studied and compared with other documented examples. Extensive research is conducted within the museum’s archives to locate purchase and acquisition documentation. Following these investigations, the inscription is transliterated, translated, and subsequently published.

Figure 5.6: Cylinder seal, WAM 42.0626 (Creative Commons Zero)

Use Case 6 – Stonehenge site

Description: Stonehenge is a well-known World Heritage site and one of the most important archaeological sites of Europe. The exact type of the stone used must be identified. The presence of possible underground or buried structures/features must be assessed. The effective relation between the position of the stone structure and past astronomic events (*i.e.*, solstice) must be clarified.

Actors: researchers

Flow: a series of on-field analyses are planned. Movable instruments are carried on the site to perform contactless analyses useful to individuate the stone type and the possible presence of ancient pigments. Ground Penetrating Radar instrument is carried on the site to survey the underground. A 3D model based on digital photogrammetry and laser scanning is created and successively analyzed within a software that recreates the natural lighting related to seasons and astronomic events in order to check if effective relations between the spatial position and the cultural meaning can be drawn.

Figure 5.7: Aerial view of Stonhenge site (Philip Henry Sharpe, Public domain, via Wikimedia Commons)

Use Case 7 – Renaissance painting

Description: a Renaissance painting ('Return from the Inn') by Pieter Brueghel the Younger stored in the Montreal Museum of Fine Arts needs a reassessment of its material components that were analysed during the second half of the 20th century through a series of material samples. New analysis must be non-invasive. New diagnostic analyses encompass RAMAN spectroscopy in order to exactly define the pigments, multispectral IR reflectography to identify pictorial layers, air quality control to verify the appropriateness of the exhibition setting. Results will be used not only by technicians to plan further possible restoration activities but also by art historians to assess possible later additions from other painters.

Actors: science conservation experts, museum curators

Flow: the painting is not moved from the current exhibition because all the analyses are carried out with portable instruments. RAMAN spectroscopy is performed on a selected range of colors to identify pigments, while multispectral IR reflectography is performed on the whole painting. Air quality measurements are carried out within the close environment where the painting is on display. All the data are uploaded into a shared database. Multispectral IR reflectography outputs are compared and matched with other similar analyses and pictures of paintings by the same author as well as different authors in order to possibly identify parts added in later times by other painters. Air quality data are

analyzed and compared with previous measurements to assess the appropriateness of the location and establish possible countermeasures.

Use Case 8 – Early Middle Ages Evangeliary

Description: The Evangeliary of Teodolinda is the cover of a lost Book of the Gospels made with gold, precious stones and enamels. It also features inserts of ancient Roman engraved gems.

Actors: researchers

Flow: The Evangeliary is temporarily moved from the permanent exhibition to a room of the Museum with restricted access to perform a petrographic analysis of gems and stones. Laboratory analyses are performed to identify the possible presence of organic glues behind the gems and the enamels, sampling also small portions.

Figure 5.8: Pieter Brueghel the Younger, The Return from the Inn (Sotheby's, Public domain, via Wikimedia Commons)

Use Case 9 – Falerii Novi archaeological site

Description: The site of Falerii Novi, located in Central Italy, has few structures but some cropmarks can be seen on satellite images along with ancient surface findings. The site must be investigated through close-range aerial images, geophysical surveys and soil analysis to verify the exact position of archaeological features in view of an archaeological campaign.

Actors: researchers

Flow: The area of the site is delimited from satellite images. A topographic survey with total station and GPS antennas is carried out. Multispectral and panchromatic aerial images of the area are acquired using drones. On a narrower area, Ground Penetration Radar (GPR) and magnetic survey are performed to individuate buried structures. Two sample of soils are also collected: a core sample to verify the extent of the archaeological deposit, and a soil sample from an archaeological operation.

Data are collected on the field over three full days of work. Images acquired with drones are processed in laboratory, obtaining digital orthophotos, three-dimensional models, and digital elevation models that are georeferenced using the data coming from the topographic survey. Data collected during the geomagnetic survey are processed as well and georeferenced. The core sample is analyzed, reconstructing the stratigraphic sequence of the location where it was sampled and stored; the soil sample from the excavation is sent to a laboratory to create thin sections that will be analyzed to understand the genesis of the deposit.

Figure 5.9: The Evangeliiary of Teodolinda, Museo del Tesoro del Duomo, Monza (Foscomartini, CC BY-SA 4.0 <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0>, via Wikimedia Commons)

Figure 5.10: The site of Falerii Novi from the satellite (image retrieved from Google Earth Pro)

5.2 GOOD PRACTICES FOR A FAIR AND INTEROPERABLE ONTOLOGY

Summary This section outlines four foundational principles for publishing and interlinking data according to the Linked Data (LD) standard, which are essential for OE. The Heritage Science Ontology adheres to these principles while aligning with the normative standards established by the Open Biological and Biomedical Ontologies (OBO) Foundry. This structured approach aims to foster collaboration and adherence to best practices in developing ontologies within the Heritage domain, ultimately enhancing their utility and integration within the broader data ecosystem.

Heath and Bizer (2011, 7–27) identify four key principles for publishing and interlinking data according to the Linked Data (LD) standard: naming things with URIs, making URIs dereferenceable, providing useful RDF information, and including links to other resources. In OE, these principles are now considered essential. First, each concept or entity—such as classes, properties, and instances—should be assigned a unique URI, serving as a universal reference point to ensure consistency and avoid ambiguity. Furthermore, URIs should provide meaningful, machine-readable information when accessed, typically in a standardized format like RDF. Dereferenceable URIs enhance ontology reuse and interoperability, making it easier for developers and systems to retrieve, understand, and integrate the ontology’s content. Lastly, a key advantage of Linked Data in OE is the ability to link to other relevant ontologies. This interconnection facilitates integration, knowledge discovery, and reuse across different domains, enriching the overall web of data. Many of these best practices have been formalized in the D2.5 FAIR Semantics Recommendations – Second Iteration deliverable, produced within the framework of the FAIRsFAIR project [Hugo et al. (2020); <https://www.fairsfair.eu/>] and have been formalized wherever possible.

As evident from this brief introduction, the application of LD principles also underscores the importance of publishing ontologies in a documented, machine-readable format as a critical step in the OE process. To ensure consistent application of these principles, the ontology here presented has been developed in compliance with the Open Biological and Biomedical Ontologies (OBO) Foundry’s normative principles. The OBO Foundry is a global community committed to fostering collaboration and shared standards in ontology development within the biomedical field (Jackson et al. 2021). Since the early 2000s, it has played a key role in organizing and guiding ontology development efforts in this domain. To support this mission, the OBO Foundry has established a set of principles designed to assess how well an ontology aligns with these standards⁵⁰. As highlighted by the H-SetIS survey (Scarpa and Valente 2024a, 545–46), many ontology projects within the Heritage field fall short of meeting the minimum requirements and best practices endorsed by larger communities such as the OBO Foundry. To address this issue, the development of the ontology here presented has adhered to the relevant OBO Foundry principles applicable to an ontology related to the Heritage domain. Specifically:

- Consistent with principle 3 (URI), the main IRI of the ontology will resolve directly to the ontology file, while the ontology’s documentation will be available at a URI resolving to the documentation page, e.g. <http://purl.org/hersci/documentation>. Among principal Globally Unique, Persistent, Resolvable Identifier (GUPRI) services are purl.org and w3id.org; a choice in this regard has not yet been made⁵¹.
- Versions of the ontology will be appropriately marked, stored, and officially released following semantic versioning principles (Preston-Werner 2024). Each stable version will be accessible through version-specific IRIs using the pattern <http://purl.org/hersci/releases/YYYY-MM-DD/hersci.owl>. Semantic versioning will also be applied to the releases available on the ontology’s GitHub repository (<https://github.com/erica-scarpa/heritage-science-ontology>).

⁵⁰ <https://obofoundry.org/principles/fp-000-summary.html> (last visit 10-10-2024).

⁵¹ <https://faircookbook.elixir-europe.org/content/recipes/infrastructure/gupri.html> (last visit 10-10-2024). Throughout this document, the use of GUPRIs based on the purl.org service is suggested, as the purl.org service was initially chosen by the editors working on the ontology discussed here. However, purl.org—currently operated by the Internet Archive (Graham 2016)—has experienced significant disruptions due to two major DDoS attacks in 2024 (Freeland 2024; Kahle 2024). Since the service has remained unavailable, the implementation of PURLs could not be completed, and the use of GUPRIs provided by the w3id.org service is currently under consideration.

- Textual definitions of classes and properties are unique, human-readable, and written in English (principle 6). The OBO Foundry principles suggest the use of Aristotelian definitions through the genus/differentia format (“a B that Cs”), but this approach can often lead to tautological or overly generic statements. Consequently, Aristotelian definitions are primarily applied to properties. In other cases, standard definitions, examples, and clarifications are used to provide clearer, more informative descriptions. To document the classes and properties, the annotation properties *example of usage* (obo:IAO_0000112)⁵², *term editor* (obo:IAO_0000117)⁵³, *editor note* (obo:IAO_0000116)⁵⁴, and *curator note* (obo:IAO_0000232)⁵⁵ of the OBO Foundry ontology ecosystem are utilized. Currently, the ontology is being developed in English, with a full Italian translation planned for the future.
- Ontology documentation has traditionally been published in the form of academic papers. However, in recent years, best practices have shifted towards documenting ontologies through metadata and comprehensive reports. To ensure the completeness of ontology documentation, Matentzoglou et al. (2018) introduced the **Minimum Information for the Reporting of an Ontology** (MIRO) guidelines, which provide a framework for producing consistent and comprehensive documentation. The OBO Foundry guidelines further recommend categorizing documentation into four types: *embedded*, *local*, *user*, and *development* documentation (principle 8 on documentation⁵⁶). The Heritage Science Ontology adheres to both the MIRO guidelines and OBO Foundry principles where applicable, with thorough documentation provided in its GitHub repository. Embedded documentation is included in the ontology’s metadata. Preliminary local documentation (*i.e.*, ontology specification) is presented in this document and will be regularly maintained and updated in the ontology repository. User documentation, will serve as a permanent reference and published through more conventional means (e.g., academic paper). Development documentation is both explicitly and implicitly provided in the ontology repository, with the CONTRIBUTING.md (<https://github.com/erica-scarpa/heritage-science-ontology/blob/main/CONTRIBUTING.md>) file detailing the process for contributing, submitting issues, and serving as a record for tracking changes, releases, contribution history, and version control.

6 HERITAGE SCIENCE ONTOLOGY: CLASSES AND PROPERTIES SPECIFICATION

6.1 ONTOLOGY METADATA

Version IRI owl:versionIRI: <https://purl.org/hersci/0.1.0>

Bibliographic citation dcterms:bibliographicCitation: (Reference to a traditional publication of the ontology, e.g. a journal article)

Created dcterms:created: 2024-09-19

Creators dcterms:creator: Erica Scarpa, Riccardo Valente

Description dcterms:description: The Heritage Science Ontology is designed to manage semantic data that deals with Heritage and Conservation Science.

⁵² Defined as «[a] phrase describing how a term should be used and/or a citation to a work which uses it. May also include other kinds of examples that facilitate immediate understanding, such as widely known prototypes or instances of a class, or cases where a relation is said to hold».

⁵³ Defined as «[n]ame of editor entering the term in the file. The term editor is a point of contact for information regarding the term. The term editor may be, but is not always, the author of the definition, which may have been worked upon by several people».

⁵⁴ Defined as «[a]n administrative note intended for its editor. It may not be included in the publication version of the ontology, so it should contain nothing necessary for end users to understand the ontology»

⁵⁵ Defined as «[a]n administrative note of use for a curator but of no use for a user».

⁵⁶ <https://obofoundry.org/principles/fp-008-documented.html>

License dcterms:license: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Title dcterms:title: Heritage Science Ontology

Preferred namespace vann:preferredNamespacePrefix: hersci

Preferred namespace URI vann:preferredNamespaceUri: <https://purl.org/hersci#>

Comment rdfs:comment: The Heritage Science Ontology by Task 4.10 (CNR ISPC, Milan) part of WP 4 of the H2IOSC project is licensed under CC BY 4.0 (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

Comment rdfs:comment: The Heritage Science Ontology by Task 4.10 (CNR ISPC, Milan) part of WP 4 of the H2IOSC project is licensed under CC BY 4.0. You are free to share (copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format) and adapt (remix, transform, and build upon the material) for any purpose, even commercially. You must give appropriate credit (by using the original ontology IRI for the whole ontology or original term IRIs for individual terms), provide a link to the license, and indicate if any changes were made. You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use

Version info owl:versionInfo: 0.1.0

Status sw:status: First draft

Prefixes @prefix: dc: <http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/>; sw: <https://www.w3.org/2003/06/sw-vocab-status/ns#>; obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo>; owl: <http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#>; rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>; xml: <http://www.w3.org/XML/1998/namespace>; xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>; bibo: <http://purl.org/ontology/bibo/>; foaf: <http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/#>; rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>; vann: <http://purl.org/vocab/vann/>; hersci: <https://purl.org/hersci#>; schema: <https://schema.org/>; dcterms: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>

6.2 CLASSES

6.2.1 Agent hersci:HSC0002 ≡ Agent foaf:Agent

Description dcterms:description: A subject that is involved at any level in actions or events related to Heritage Science.

Superclass of: Group hersci:HSC0027, Organization hersci:HSC0045, Person hersci:HSC0026

6.2.1.1 Group hersci:HSC0027 ≡ Group foaf:Group

Description dcterms:description: An actor that is composed by more than one person that is at any level involved in Heritage Science

Examples of usage obo:IAO_0000112: The Beatles (<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q1299>), a rock band; The Blue Rider (<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q117035>), a group of expressionist artists

Subclass of Agent hersci:HSC0002

6.2.1.2 Organization hersci:HSC0045 ≡ Organization foaf:Organization

Description dcterms:description: A kind of agent corresponding to social institutions such as companies, societies etc.

Examples of usage obo:IAO_0000112: The Institute of Heritage Science of the Italian National Research Council (<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q125592016>)

Subclass of Agent hersci:HSC0002

6.2.1.3 Person `hersci:HSC0026` ≡ Person `foaf:Person`

Description `dcterms:description`: A human being that is at any level involved in Heritage Science

Examples of usage `obo:IAO_0000112`: Gilgamesh (<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q159709>), the main character of the 'Epic of Gilgamesh'; Myron (<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q192211>), a greek sculptor from the 5th century BC; Pope Julius II (<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q80516>) as commissioner of St. Peter's Basilica

Subclass of Agent `hersci:HSC0002`

6.2.2 Collection `hersci:HSC0005`

Description `dcterms:description`: An ensemble of Heritage objects that is usually managed by public or private agents

Examples of usage `obo:IAO_0000112`: The Department of Near Eastern Antiquities of the Louvre Museum (<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3044751>); The Rosenwald Collection at the National Gallery of Art in Washington D.C. (<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q62274660>)

6.2.3 Critical Edition `hersci:HSC0007`

Description `dcterms:description`: An ideal reconstruction of a text that is made by philologists by comparing several versions of the Textual Witness

Examples of usage `obo:IAO_0000112`: 'Die Fragmente der Vorsokratiker' by Hermann Diels and Walther Kranz (1903; <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q1212533>); The edition of the Hammurapi code by Father Jean-Vincent Scheil (1902) in the fourth volume of 'Mémoires de la Délégation en Perse

6.2.4 Documentation `hersci:HSC0008`

Description `dcterms:description`: Any element that aims at recording Heritage entities, regardless of the form or the medium

Superclass of: Visual Documentation `hersci:HSC0034`, Written Documentation `hersci:HSC0033`

6.2.4.1 Visual Documentation `hersci:HSC0034`

Description `dcterms:description`: Any kind of Documentation that record Heritage entities using visual media

Examples of usage `obo:IAO_0000112`: The picture of the Great Pyramid and the Sphinx taken by Francis Frith in 1858 (https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:The_Great_Pyramid_and_the_Sphinx.jpg).

Subclass of Documentation `hersci:HSC0008`

6.2.4.2 Written Documentation `hersci:HSC0033`

Description `dcterms:description`: Any kind of Documentation that records Heritage entities using a written text

Examples of usage `obo:IAO_0000112`: Diary 49 by Joseph Mathia Svoboda dated to the 1890s and documenting his journeys in the Middle East, currently preserved at Washington University

Subclass of Documentation `hersci:HSC0008`

6.2.5 Ductus `hersci:HSC0009`

Description `dcterms:description`: The characteristics of strokes that make glyphs, including speed, direction and sequence

Examples of usage obo:IAO_0000112: The Ductus used to write the version of Magna Carta included in the Cotton MS. Augustus II. 106 manuscript from Sir Robert Cotton's (<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q333098>) library

6.2.6 Inscription hersci:HSC0040

Description dcterms:description: Any transfer of a Text or of an element that conveys meaning on a material and potentially persistent surface with any technique

Examples of usage obo:IAO_0000112: The carved glyphs of the Manishtushu Obelisk (<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q6749917>); The glyphs impressed on clay of the Prüfening dedicatory inscription (<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q685784>); The ink on a page that carries the poem 'Un perro ha muerto' by Pablo Neruda (<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q34189>) on a copy of the book 'Jardín de invierno' (1974)

6.2.7 Institution hersci:HSC0013

Description dcterms:description: Any public or private body that is involved in Heritage Science at any level

Examples of usage obo:IAO_0000112: The Library of Congress (<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q131454>) in Washington DC; The Museum of Innocence (<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q15961492>) in Istanbul; The Ukrainian Ministry of Culture and Strategic Communications (<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q67121433>)

6.2.8 Language hersci:HSC0014

Description dcterms:description: Any system made of sounds, words and grammar that is used to communicate among human beings

Examples of usage obo:IAO_0000112: Inuinnaqtun (<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q28070>); Latin (<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q397>); Na'vi (<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q316939>); Swahili (<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q7838>)

6.2.9 Material hersci:HSC0015

Description dcterms:description: Any kind of tangible matter that can be modified by human beings to fulfill their needs

Examples of usage obo:IAO_0000112: Bread (<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q7802>); Feather (<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q81025>); Marble (<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q40861>); Wood (<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q287>)

6.2.10 Nation hersci:HSC0016

Description dcterms:description: An administrative division that sets both spatial and cultural boundaries and gives a cultural orientation to the population that lives within

Examples of usage obo:IAO_0000112: Canada (<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q16>); Italy (<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q38>); Myanmar (<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q836>); Panama (<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q804>)

6.2.11 Non Textual Element hersci:HSC0017

Description dcterms:description: Any element related to an Inscription or a part of it that does not belong to any known writing system

Superclass of Integral Element hersci:HSC0036, Non Integral Element hersci:HSC0035

6.2.11.1 Integral Element hersci:HSC0036

Description dterms:description: Any element related to an Inscription or a part of it that does not belong to any known writing system and has a direct relation with the content of the Inscription

Examples of usage obo:IAO_0000112: One of the thirteen seal impressions on the Seleucid cuneiform tablet BM 105197 bearing the text of a templar prebend (<https://cdli.mpiwg-berlin.mpg.de/artifacts/342293>)

Subclass of: Non Textual Element hersci:HSC0017

6.2.11.2 Non Integral Element hersci:HSC0035

Description dterms:description: Any element related to an Inscription or a part of it that does not belong to any known writing system that has not a direct relation with the content of the Inscription

Examples of usage obo:IAO_0000112: The illuminated decorations on the left side of f.1v of BnF, Ms. Français 2810 (<https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/btv1b52000858n>)

Subclass of: Non Textual Element hersci:HSC0017

6.2.12 Place hersci:HSC0020

Description dterms:description: Any physical place a human being directly or indirectly interacts with

Examples of usage obo:IAO_0000112: ...

Superclass of: Archaeological Site hersci:HSC0041, Complex hersci:HSC0042, Structure hersci:HSC0043

6.2.12.1 Archaeological Site hersci:HSC0041

Description dterms:description: Any place where material evidence of the human past can be found and eventually used to reconstruct human history

Examples of usage obo:IAO_0000112: The Machu Picchu on the Peruvian Andes (<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q676203>); The ancient Roman city of Pompeii (<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q43332>)

Subclass of: Place hersci:HSC0020

6.2.12.2 Complex hersci:HSC0042

Description dterms:description: Any group of independent or semi-independent structures related among them.

Examples of usage obo:IAO_0000112: The Castle of Good Hope in South Africa (<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q1049562>); The Forbidden City in Beijing (<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q80290>)

Subclass of: Place hersci:HSC0020

6.2.12.3 Structure hersci:HSC0043

Description dterms:description: Any built-up element realized by human beings for any purpose

Examples of usage obo:IAO_0000112: A given toguna (<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3530380>) in a Dogon (<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q215583>) village of Mali

(<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q912>); The Golden Gate
(<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q44440>) on the San Francisco Bay; The Leaning Tower of Pisa
(<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q39054>)

Subclass of: Place hersci:HSC0020

6.2.12.4 Spatial Division hersci:HSC0044

Description dcterms:description: Any system of division of space at any scale

Examples of usage obo:IAO_0000112: A given room within a given structure
(<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q180516>); A sector within a larger area
(<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q219858>)

Subclass of: Archaeological Site hersci:HSC0041, Complex hersci:HSC0042, Structure hersci:HSC0043

6.2.13 Tangible Entity hersci:HSC0018

Description dcterms:description: Any tangible entity that can be considered as Heritage

Examples of usage obo:IAO_0000112: The DeLorean DMC-12
(<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q370524>) automobile featured in the 'Back to the Future' Movies;
The headdress (<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q104869799>) of Puabi, queen of Ur ; The main royal
palace (Gyeongbokgung) of the Chosŏn dynasty in Seoul (<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q482485>)

6.2.14 Tangible Entity Component hersci:HSC0019

Description dcterms:description: Any material element, not necessarily existing as an independent Object, that belongs to a Tangible Entity

Examples of usage obo:IAO_0000112: The color layer representing the skin of Christ in Michelangelo's Crucifix (<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q1572984>) located in the Church of Santo Spirito in Florence

6.2.15 Script hersci:HSC0021

Description dcterms:description: A specific style or form of writing, often associated with a particular time period, culture, or purpose

Examples of usage obo:IAO_0000112: The Carolingian minuscule
(<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q785729>); The Roman cursive
(<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q1285080>)

6.2.16 Textual Witness hersci:HSC0023

Description dcterms:description: Any particular form of a given Text, including variants and errors

Examples of usage obo:IAO_0000112: The textual witness of RIME 2.1.2.13 displayed on the ceremonial mace-head (CBS 14933) kept in the Penn Museum, Philadelphia

6.2.17 Writing System hersci:HSC0025

Description dcterms:description: A structured set of symbols and rules representing the sounds, meanings, and grammar of a given language

Examples of usage obo:IAO_0000112: Cuneiform (<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q401>); Egyptian hieroglyphs (<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q132659>); Latin alphabet (<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q8229>)

6.3 OBJECT PROPERTIES

6.3.1 belongs to hersci:HSP0001

Description dterms:description: A relation between two particulars where 'b' owns the property of 'a' or has it on loan

6.3.2 conveys hersci:HSP0003

Description dterms:description: A relation between an Inscription 'a' and a Text 'b' that is transmitted by 'a'

6.3.3 covers hersci:HSP0004

Description dterms:description: A physical relation between two material particulars where 'b' is physically covered by 'a'

6.3.4 has action hersci:HSP0005

Description dterms:description: A relation between a Tangible Entity and an Action

6.3.5 has assumed material hersci:HSP0007

Description dterms:description: A relation between two particulars where the 'b' is a material and constitutes the matter of 'a' when accurate scientific analysis about the real nature of the material itself lack

6.3.6 has element hersci:HSP0009

Description dterms:description: A relation between two particulars where 'b' is a Non Textual Element of a Tangible Entity 'a'

6.3.7 has ductus hersci:HSP0010

Description dterms:description: A relation between an Inscription 'a' and a Ductus 'b' where 'b' defines the direction, speed, orientation of strokes of 'a'

6.3.8 has collection hersci:HSP0011

Description dterms:description: A relation between two particulars where 'b' keeps 'a' in a given collection

6.3.9 has critical edition hersci:HSP0012

Description dterms:description: A relation between two particulars where 'b' is the reconstructed original text of 'a'

6.3.10 has created hersci:HSP0013

Description dterms:description: A relation between two particulars where 'b' was created by 'a' at multiple levels (conceptualization, design, material creation)

6.3.11 has finding place hersci:HSP0014

Description dcterms:description: A relation between two particulars where 'a' is a Tangible Entity and 'b' is a Place where 'a' was found

6.3.12 belongs to organization hersci:HSP0016

Description dcterms:description: A relation between two particulars where 'b' is an Institution and 'a' is the subject that belongs to 'b'

6.3.13 has language hersci:HSP0017

Description dcterms:description: A relation between two particulars where 'b' is a Language and 'a' is a Textual Witness or a Critical Edition

6.3.14 has material hersci:HSP0018

Description dcterms:description: A relation between two particulars where 'b' is the Material that entirely or partially constitutes a Tangible Entity 'a'

6.3.15 has primary place hersci:HSP0019

Description dcterms:description: A relation between two particulars where 'b' is the Place where the Tangible Entity 'a' is currently located or was located as a primary location

6.3.16 has place hersci:HSP0020

Description dcterms:description: A relation between two particulars where 'b' is a Place and 'a' is an Agent whose main office or building is in 'b'

6.3.17 has script hersci:HSP0021

Description dcterms:description: A relation between two particulars where 'b' is a Script and 'a' is an Inscription

6.3.18 has writing system hersci:HSP0022

Description dcterms:description: A relation between two particulars where 'b' is a Writing System and 'a' is a Textual Witness

6.3.19 has written hersci:HSP0023

Description dcterms:description: A relation between two particulars where 'b' is an Inscription and 'a' is an Agent who has materially created an Inscription

6.3.20 is author of hersci:HSP0024

Description dcterms:description: A relation between two particulars where 'a' is an Agent and 'b' is a given entity that was realized by 'a'

6.3.21 is composed by hersci:HSP0025

Description dcterms:description: A relation between two particulars where 'b' is a Tangible Entity Component and 'a' is a Tangible Entity or a Tangible Entity Component of which a component is 'b'

6.3.22 is covered by hersci:HSP0026

Description dcterms:description: A relation between two particulars where 'a' and 'b' are both Tangible Entity Components so that 'a' has a physical relation that normally demands that 'b' is more recent than 'a'

6.3.23 is documented by hersci:HSP0027

Description dcterms:description: A relation between two particulars where 'a' is a given entity and 'b' is a given document

6.3.24 is editor of hersci:HSP0028

Description dcterms:description: A relation between two particulars where 'b' is a Critical Edition and 'a' is an Agent

6.3.25 is part of hersci:HSP0029

Description dcterms:description: A relation between two particulars where 'b' is the Group to which 'a' belongs to

6.3.26 contained in place schema:containedInPlace

Description dcterms:description: A relation between two particulars where 'a' is a spatial entity that contains 'b'

6.4 DATA PROPERTIES

6.4.1 accessibility hersci:HSD0001

Description dcterms:description: Degree of physical accessibility of an entity

6.4.2 ancient name hersci:HSD0002

Description dcterms:description: Ancient name of a place

6.4.3 current name hersci:HSD0007

Description dcterms:description: Current name of a place

6.4.4 diameter hersci:HSD0008

Description dcterms:description: Measurement of the diameter of a given Tangible Entity

6.4.5 excavation identifier hersci:HSD0010

Description dcterms:description: Identification number of an archeological finding given during the excavation process

6.4.6 has hand hersci:HSD0011

Description dcterms:description: A specific handwriting associated with an identified or unidentified Agent

6.4.7 height herisci:HSD0012

Description dcterms:description: Measurement of the height of a given Tangible Entity

6.4.8 other identifier herisci:HSD0013

Description dcterms:description: Any identifier associated with a Tangible Entity other than the excavation identifier and/or museum identifier

6.4.9 legibility herisci:HSD0014

Description dcterms:description: Degree of clarity determining how easily individual characters, words, and sentences can be visually recognized

6.4.10 length herisci:HSD0015

Description dcterms:description: Measurement of the length of a give Tangible Entity

6.4.11 material herisci:HSD0017

Description dcterms:description: Any physical substance of a given Tangible Entity or one of its components

6.4.12 museum identifier herisci:HSD0018

Description dcterms:description: An identifier given by a Museum or other institution to a given Tangible Entity

6.4.13 state of preservation herisci:HSD0021

Description dcterms:description: Current physical condition of an artifact, structure, or site

6.4.14 type herisci:HSD0022

Description dcterms:description: Categorization of a Tangible Entity according to function and shape

6.4.15 width herisci:HSD0023

Description dcterms:description: Measurement of the width of a given Tangible Entity

6.5 CLASSES AND PROPERTIES STILL UNDER DISCUSSION

Several classes and properties remain under discussion, including those related to the management of scholarly references. One proposed approach involves adding a **Bibliographic Citation** class, defined as «A reference that provides information about a specific element within the Heritage context». However, a more efficient approach for managing bibliographic resources may be to reuse established bibliographic ontologies, such as the Bibliographic Ontology (BiBO) (<http://purl.org/ontology/bibo>⁵⁷).

Similarly, discussions are ongoing regarding the classes involved in managing time and temporal entities. In the Heritage Science Ontology, time is considered both as historical periodization (e.g., the Neo-Sumerian period) and as an archaeological timescale (e.g., the Iron Age). Additionally, time can refer to contemporary dates relevant to heritage entities (e.g., the date a specific TE underwent diagnostic analysis). Since most ontologies have unique approaches to modeling time, there is an effort to adopt a standard by reusing the Time Ontology in OWL (OWL-Time), currently a W3C

⁵⁷ <https://h-setis.cnr.it/ontologies/16>.

Candidate Recommendation Draft (Cox and Little 2022). This ontology relies on «an algebra of binary relations on intervals (e.g., meets, overlaps, during)» developed by James Allen and George Ferguson (Allen and Ferguson 1997).

Logical relations, such as domain/range constraints, asymmetry, and functional constraints, are currently under consideration, as their safe implementation necessitates a testing environment to prevent unintended inference consequences. Some seemingly innocuous statements, like “every Inscription must have a Textual Witness” (otherwise it would be classified as an uninscribed TE), require careful handling. While it is indeed true that every `her sci:HSC0040` Inscription must convey at least one `her sci:HSC0023` Textual Witness, challenges arise when a `her sci:HSC0023` Textual Witness exists but cannot be interpreted, such as in the case of an undeciphered language.

FINAL REMARKS AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

Of the four steps in the LOT methodology, the first two are the most crucial in developing an ontology. With a strong emphasis on adhering to the FAIR principles and the Linked Data (LD) paradigm, the subsequent steps in ontology development will involve the following:

1. Enhancing the content of the H-SeTIS database, as it serves as a key working tool for the development team. Improvements to the curated bibliography will transform H-SeTIS into a valuable resource hub for the community interested in developing semantic artefacts in the Heritage field.
2. Organizing one or more roundtable discussions with domain experts to assess the community’s requirements for data retrievability and reasoning. This process will include developing detailed scenarios, covering use cases beyond the expertise of the development team.
3. Finalizing the remaining classes and properties still under discussion, incorporating insights from discussions with domain experts.
4. Provide alignment options with the Common Semantic Framework, in particular with the H2IOSCro (H2IOSC reference ontology), still under development.
5. Conducting tests on a sample dataset and formulating a set of SPARQL queries for validation.
6. Publishing the scientific outcomes of the research conducted by Task 4.10 through traditional means (*i.e.*, research papers).
7. Publishing the finalized ontology.

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ANNEX: BRIEF OVERVIEW OF THE ONTOLOGIES FOR THE “ILLUMINATED MANUSCRIPT PILOT” DEVELOPED IN E-RIHS.IT DIGILAB PLATFORM

DIGILAB is set to become the digital access platform for the Italian node of the European Infrastructure for Heritage Science (E-RIHS). Its primary challenge is to integrate data, tools, and services into a unified digital environment, maximizing accessibility and interoperability while offering advanced services for processing, analyzing, and correlating data. The architecture of DIGILAB aligns with the principles established by ESFRI [ESRI, 2024] and is consistent with the goals of cluster projects in the Cultural Heritage domain [ECCP, 2024]. At the national level, DIGILAB's design follows the guidelines of the National Plan for the Digitization of Cultural Heritage [INPDCC, 2024], developed by the Central Institute for the Digitization of Cultural Heritage - Digital Library of the Italian Ministry of Cultural Heritage. This plan outlines the strategic vision for digital innovation in managing heritage assets. Additionally, DIGILAB must comply with EU data management principles (FAIR, Open Research Data) and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) initiative [EOSC, 2024].

Inside DIGILAB, a Pilot Project is a focused initiative designed to explore specific knowledge domains within the broader context of the DIGILAB platform. These projects provide vertical, domain-specific experiences allowing in-depth testing and refinement of methodologies, tools, and data integration strategies. Each Pilot Project is interconnected with the DIGILAB knowledge base, enabling the efficient reading and writing of data, and implements a tailored interaction model that addresses the unique requirements of the respective domain.

By adopting a bottom-up approach through these Pilot Projects, we can effectively define platform requirements and develop ontologies for various knowledge sub-domains. This strategy allows us to begin with specific, manageable use cases that reflect real-world research needs, ensuring that the system architecture is relevant and user-friendly. Such an approach promotes collaboration and interoperability among different disciplines, ultimately enhancing the overall effectiveness of the DIGILAB platform.

In the following, we selected the Illuminated Manuscripts Pilot Project as a key use case. This project will focus on implementing the ontology for manuscripts, incorporating aspects of Art History, Codicology, and Palaeography as well as other material and immaterial elements. Additionally, it will integrate the Diagnostic Investigation ontology for scientific analyses.

1.2 ONTOLOGY MODELING METHODOLOGY

The development process began with the decision to use the CIDOC-CRM (and the other compatible models such as CRMsci, CMRdig, CRMtex, and LRMoo) as a foundational framework to ensure interoperability within the heritage science domain. By adopting this standard, we aimed to enhance compatibility with existing cultural heritage databases and systems while maintaining the flexibility to expand the ontology for specific research needs.

Given the inherent complexity and evolving nature of cultural heritage knowledge, the ontology development process should incorporate multiple cycles of validation and refinement. Continuous feedback from domain experts is essential to identify gaps, inconsistencies, or overly rigid structures. Iterative cycles of evaluation and adjustment allow for ongoing improvement, ensuring that the ontology remains adaptable and aligned with both current research needs and emerging trends. This iterative approach ensures that as new data, methods, and perspectives emerge, the ontology can evolve to meet the changing requirements of the field.

To achieve this, the ontology development process is organized into a series of well-defined steps, each addressing a specific key aspect. It begins with *scope definition*, followed by *systematic information gathering*, and then progresses through iterative *conceptualization*, *structuring*, and *formalization*. Each phase incorporates feedback and refinement to ensure the ontology remains flexible and relevant. This structured yet adaptive process allows the ontology to accommodate the

diverse needs of the Heritage Science field while ensuring interoperability and alignment with evolving research priorities.

1.2 THE ILLUMINATED MANUSCRIPTS PILOT

Task 7.5 of the WP7 within the H2IOSC project includes a Pilot project dedicated to ancient, illuminated manuscripts. The pilot aims to implement a virtual research environment dedicated to illuminated manuscripts analyzed by diagnostic investigations to create shared and participatory knowledge. This virtual space will offer access to heterogeneous scientific data and a set of tools for data exchange, analysis, integration, and visualization (WP3, WP4, WP6).

First, the repository will host the data related to the manuscripts investigated by the mobile laboratories (MOLAB) of the E-RIHS. Subsequently, it will be enriched with resources produced by other research groups, institutes, individual researchers engaged for many years on the same themes. The project will link up with other important national and international initiatives.

The HUB will be exposed on the E-RIHS Digital Platform, and it will be aligned with the FAIR data principles also through data management policies given to all data providers. The *Illuminated Manuscript* is designed to welcome overtime data, experiences, and contributions from several research groups, Institutes, and individual researchers who wish to share the results of their studies on illuminated manuscripts.

The design of the VRE meets the needs expressed by scholars from various scientific fields interested in book artifacts, including experts in diagnostics and humanists with diverse backgrounds.

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Over the past 20 years, MOLAB has studied several illuminated manuscripts, some of which have significant historical and artistic value [Romani, 2020] [Brunetti et al., 2016]. The idea of getting the knowledge gained from these studies in the VRE stems from the recognition of the contribution they can make to the understanding of the codices and their material complexity. The information obtained from complementary analytical investigations provides valuable insights into the creation of manuscripts. This includes details about the materials used, execution techniques, the organization of the craft workshop, and the level of specialization of illuminators involved. Additionally, it can offer indications that are useful for reconstructing the chronology of execution and identifying the places of production. Among these, we are implementing in our Pilot the IIIF framework [IIIF, 2024], the MIRADOR viewer [Mirador], and the ATON framework to immersive fruition of 3D models of manuscripts [Fanini et al., 2021].

The pilot *Illuminated Manuscripts VRE* is based on the experience gained in two research projects that have illuminated codices as their object: DataSpace-ISPC [Bucciero A. et al, 2023] and Codex 4D [Pietroni, 2023] [Pietroni et al, 2024], to which we refer for an overview of the main national and international initiatives in the same field.

1.3 THE ILLUMINATED MANUSCRIPTS ONTOLOGY

The development of ontologies for the manuscript domain within the DIGILAB platform focuses on modeling various aspects essential for creating the Heritage Digital Twin [Niccolucci et al., 2022] of manuscripts. In this initial phase, we focused on a specific form, namely the codex, whose definition does not suffer of ambiguity. It is in fact a “libro formato da fogli piegati in due (bifogli) e riuniti in uno o più fascicoli, cuciti mediante un filo lungo la linea di piegatura” [Maniaci, 1998]. The ontological model currently in development will describe the codex in all its complexity, as a physical object vehicle of symbolic content. The Manus Ontology aims to model information for implementing the Illuminated manuscripts Hub pilot. After identifying the key concepts, assessing the available technologies, and analyzing the entities provided by CIDOC CRM and its extensions, Manus Ontology introduces new classes and properties to address the needs of the pilot. This process incorporates

CIDOC-CRM and its extensions—CRMSci, CRMDig, CRMTex, and LRMoo—to ensure that the domain's specific concepts and terminology are accurately represented and aligned with broader heritage science standards. These ontologies will support the formalization of the DIGILAB knowledge base, which will also be used by the Illuminated Manuscripts pilot project.

The primary aim of this effort is to create data models and tools that enable the management of both data and metadata related to the Heritage Digital Twin of manuscripts. The scope of the modeling process includes several key areas:

- **Codicological elements**, such as the layout of the manuscript page, critical for understanding the manuscript's structure.
- **The main concepts for studying the text**, including transcription and translation of textual elements.
- **Material and immaterial aspects of the illumination** of a manuscript.
- **Representation of Assumptions** related to the interpretation of physical and symbolic elements of the manuscripts, allowing for the incorporation of scholarly perspectives.
- **Diagnostic investigation**, focusing on scientific analyses that reveal the material properties and condition of manuscripts, contributing to conservation and restoration efforts.
- **Connection with digital representations**, ensuring that the material and immaterial aspects of manuscripts are linked to their corresponding digital counterparts, forming the foundation for the Heritage Digital Twin.

We are following the methodology described, which outlines a structured approach for developing ontologies through iterative cycles of validation and refinement. Currently, we are in the preliminary stage of formalization, where the foundational concepts and relationships are being defined in collaboration with domain experts. This early stage is crucial for ensuring that the ontology aligns with both the specific needs of the manuscript domain and the broader objectives of the DIGILAB platform. To guide the development of these ontologies, we have formulated a series of competency questions that address critical aspects of information management related to manuscripts. These questions will help refine our understanding of the requirements and functionalities necessary for effective data modeling and ensure that the resulting ontologies adequately support user needs within the context of the Heritage Digital Twin.

Diagnostic investigations play a crucial role in heritage science, as they provide detailed information on works of art, monuments, historical artifacts, and other cultural heritages. The techniques used range from the use of optical technologies, such as multispectral photography, to scientific methods such as spectroscopy and tomography, which allow composition analysis, the state of conservation and degradation processes of materials without compromising the integrity of the object.

Hence, the ontology modelling process requires a structured approach due to the different investigation techniques and types of objects to be studied. The ontology of analytic investigations was modelled using the same steps (scope definition, systematic information gathering, iterative conceptualization, structuring, and formalization) of the methodology as that applied to illuminated manuscript modelling. We focused on real scenarios of diagnostic activities whose information must be reported in the ontology. In particular, the following case studies were considered:

- **MOLAB-IT (MOBILE LABORATORY) - Spot diagnostic techniques.** This case study describes the diagnostic activities performed by mobile laboratories. MOLAB (MOBILE LABORATORY) is a world-class distributed infrastructure that consists of key laboratories across 10 European countries providing coherent access, under a unified management structure, to a set of mobile equipment and related competencies, for in-situ non-destructive measurements of artworks, collections, monuments, and sites. The analysis may be orientated towards art-historical or

archaeological questions (execution techniques, dating, etc.); assessing the state of conservation of artefacts; determining or testing the optimal preservation strategy to slow down alteration processes; monitoring conservation treatments and, informing a risk assessment. All the techniques are non-invasive, so there is strictly no sampling or contact with the surface under exam. In this case study, we consider only the activity of Italian laboratories and the spot diagnostic techniques such as Raman (785 nm, conventional e microSORS), UV-Vis-NIR fluorescence, UV-Vis-NIR reflectance, and XRD - XRF;

- **MOLAB-IT (MOBILE LABORATORY) - Imaging diagnostic techniques.** This case is like the previous one but is focused on imaging techniques such as Macro XRF/VIS NIR Hyperspectral mapping Micro XRF mapping, Mid-FTIR hyperspectral imaging and, Optical Coherence Tomography;
- **Remote Sensing and Geophysics Analyses.** The case study aims to analyze in a detail the diagnostic processes relating to non-intrusive methods of surveying the sub-surface using techniques such as Ground Penetrating Radar, Georesistivity meters, Magnetic gradiometer and, Magnetic gradiometer using a drone, with a particular focus on the activities carried out and the actors involved;
- **2D/3D Digitalization and Survey Techniques.** The case study is focused on the 2D digitization using Reflectance Transformation Imaging (RTI) methods that capture a subject's shapes and colors to reveal surface information invisible under normal examination. Some applied techniques are photogrammetry, 2D digitization using planetary scanner and large format scanner, Terrestrial Laser Scanner (TLS), Simultaneous Localization and, Mapping (SLAM) survey;

The main investigation ontology objects will be reported in the following section based on the elements discovered in the analyzed case studies:

- **investigation_campaign:** An investigation campaign refers to a structured series of research activities aimed at collecting and analyzing data within a heritage science domain. In the field of heritage, an investigation campaign typically involves the use of various scientific, archaeological, or historical methods to examine artifacts, sites, or documents. The purpose is to gather comprehensive insights about the subject of study, often involving interdisciplinary collaboration and the use of both traditional and cutting-edge technologies.
- **investigation_activity:** Investigation activities in the cultural heritage field involve systematic processes aimed at applying a specific technique and equipment studying, documenting, and preserving historical artifacts, monuments, and sites. These activities may include digital scanning, chemical analysis, X-ray photo, all designed to uncover and understand the historical, artistic, and cultural significance of heritage objects. By gathering detailed information on materials, techniques, provenance, and conditions, investigation activities help inform conservation efforts, contribute to academic research, and support the development of digital resources like ontologies, ensuring that cultural heritage is accurately represented and preserved for future generations.
- **equipment:** this entity describes specialized equipment. This equipment includes tools for non-invasive analysis, such as X-ray fluorescence (XRF), 3D laser scanners, infrared imaging, and multispectral cameras, which help researchers study the materials, structures, and conditions of objects without damaging them. Other important equipment includes drones for aerial surveys, conservation tools for restoration work, and digital databases for cataloging and managing heritage collections. The use of advanced equipment not only aids in protecting and conserving cultural assets but also enhances the ability to accurately study and interpret historical artifacts and sites.

- **Investigation_Technique:** Investigation technique refers to the various scientific and methodological approaches used to examine, analyze, and understand artifacts, sites, and documents. These techniques range from non-invasive methods, such as photogrammetry, 3D scanning, and multispectral imaging, to more detailed scientific analyses, including radiocarbon dating, DNA analysis, and chemical composition testing. The choice of technique depends on the type of artifact or site being studied, ensuring accurate data collection to guide conservation efforts and support scholarly research.
- **Software:** Software refers to diagnostic software used to analyze, monitor, and assess the condition of artifacts, artworks, and historical sites. This software helps experts conduct non-invasive diagnostics by processing data collected from various investigation techniques. By integrating data from different sources, diagnostic software enables cultural heritage professionals to make informed decisions about preservation strategies and restoration efforts, ensuring that historical objects and sites are safeguarded for future generations.
- **Investigation_Activity_outputData:** The data output from investigation activities consists of the results and findings gathered through various research and analysis techniques. This data can take many forms, including high-resolution images, 3D models, chemical compositions, material analyses, environmental conditions, and dating results. Depending on the investigation technique used, the output may include quantitative measurements (such as element concentrations from spectroscopy), qualitative assessments (such as condition reports), or visual representations (like photogrammetry models).

The full ontology, its development process and the detailed description of all entities, properties and relationships will be available in the deliverables of the work packages WP3 and WP7 of H2IOSC project.

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